

FOREWORD

If you are interested in scientific research and discoveries, in the popular media these days, the majority of what you hear is about particle accelerators / particle physics, high energy physics, cosmic particles, space travel, but mostly something about cosmological topics like the Big Bang, the expansion of the universe, black holes, wormholes etc., and of course climate change. All this is currently quite 'in vogue'.

Nevertheless, there are numerous 'classical' physics topics that - although seemingly relegated to the background - are being intensively researched and not infrequently produce important, unexpected and impressive results.

In my opinion, this includes the field of solid state physics, in particular crystal physics. Powerful mathematical tools, such as group theory, as applied in the theory of the phase transitions (Landau's Theory), not seldom lead to new theoretical insights. Since crystals are touchable, material substances, one can concretely measure their properties and compare these with the predictions. In this way, for example, materials with specific properties can be developed.

My interest in this paper lies mainly in the description and determination of the elasticity of crystals that have undergone a phase transition. Certain crystals exhibit so-called ferroelastic properties (by analogy with ferromagnetic and ferroelectric crystals). This group often shows different and also extreme elastic constants and deformations, which have to be measured and described. At this point I also point to a collection of articles I wrote in 2017. There it is about Landau's Theory in general and applied to a number of concrete phase transitions.

In the following article, in addition to the basics of anisotropic elasticity, various investigation possibilities were discussed in detail in connection with selected crystals.

So, it remains to wish you happy reading.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

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Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

1. Displacements in Continua

- Every point of a continuum shall have moved from a position, described by \vec{r} to its new position, described by \vec{r}'
- The displacement of that point can be described by

$$\vec{s}(\vec{r}) = \vec{r}' - \vec{r} \quad (1)$$

- Generally, displacements can be decomposed in a pure translation, rotation and distortion
- Further it is assumed that all displacements are small, and located closely to the origin of the System of Coordinates (SoC)^{*)}
- The shift of the origin of SoC ($\vec{r} = 0$) is described by

$$\vec{r}'(0) = \vec{s}(0) = \vec{s}_0 \quad (2)$$

Note: The contents of chapters 1.-3. base mainly on dedicated textbooks (e.g. /1/,/2/)

^{*)} Note: SoC means the (Cartesian) crystal-physical system of coordinates (x, y, z) – particularly defined for each crystal classes

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- Taylor-Series' development of \vec{s} at $\vec{r} = 0$ yields

$$\vec{s}(\vec{r}) = \vec{s}_0 + \vec{r} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \circ \vec{s} \right)_{\vec{r}=0} = \vec{s}_0 + \vec{r} \vec{U} = \vec{s}_0 + \vec{r} \vec{U}^a + \vec{r} \vec{U}^s \quad (3)$$

with: \vec{U} = 2nd rank tensor of displacement
 \vec{U}^a = anti-symmetric part
 \vec{U}^s = symmetric part
 \vec{s}_0 = shift of the origin of SoC

Antisymmetric Tensor – Representation of the Rotation

- Having done the ('standard') decomposition of tensor \vec{U} , for the anti-symmetric part follows explicitly:

$$\vec{U}^a = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \circ \vec{s} - \vec{s} \circ \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \right)_0 = \sum_{i,k} \vec{e}_i \circ \vec{e}_k U_{i,k}^a = \sum_{i,k} \vec{e}_i \circ \vec{e}_k \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_k}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_k} \right)_0 \quad (4)$$

*) Note: Expressions of the kind $\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \circ \vec{s} \right)$ are called dyad (\circ) and represent a tensor, not a scalar product!

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- Looking closer at the tensor's components we find:
 - $\vec{\vec{U}}^a$ is indeed anti-symmetric: $\vec{\vec{U}}^a = -\vec{\vec{U}}^a$, $U_{ik}^a = -U_{ki}^a$
 - $\vec{\vec{U}}^a$ has 3 independent components, which means that it can be equivalently represented by an (axial) vector $\varphi_k = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{klm} U_{lm}^a$

- The rotational displacement can be written as (using (3), (4)):

$$\vec{s}_{rot}(\vec{r}) = \vec{r} \vec{\vec{U}}^a = \frac{1}{2} \vec{r} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \circ \vec{s} - \vec{s} \circ \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \right)_0 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \times \vec{s} \right)_0 \times \vec{r} \equiv \vec{\varphi} \times \vec{r} \quad (5)$$

whereby $\vec{\varphi}$ denotes the infinitesimal small (axial) rotation vector.

- Comparison yields:

$$\vec{\varphi} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \times \vec{s} \right)_0 = \frac{1}{2} (rot \vec{s})_0, \quad \text{and in components: } \varphi_i = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial x_m} \quad (6)$$

- In particular we obtain, invoking eqs. (6) and (4):

$$\varphi_1 = \varphi_x = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial s_y}{\partial z} \right)_0 = U_{yz}^a = -U_{zy}^a \quad (7a)$$

Note: ε_{klm} is the so called Levi-Civita symbol

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$$\varphi_2 = \varphi_y = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial s_z}{\partial x} \right)_0 = U_{zx}^a = -U_{xz}^a \quad (7b)$$

$$\varphi_3 = \varphi_z = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial s_x}{\partial y} \right)_0 = U_{xy}^a = -U_{yx}^a \quad (7c)$$

- The resulting (infinitesimal) overall rotation calculates as the sum acc. to:

$$\vec{\varphi} = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_1 \vec{e}_1 \\ \varphi_2 \vec{e}_2 \\ \varphi_3 \vec{e}_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with } \vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3 \text{ being the unit vectors along the x-,y-,z-axes of the SoC} \quad (8)$$

Symmetric Tensor – Representation of the Distortion (Strain)

- The symmetric part \vec{U}^s of tensor \vec{U} is named deformation-, respectively strain tensor and is often denoted as \vec{S} (capital S - for strain)

$$\vec{U}^s = \vec{S} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \circ \vec{s} + \vec{s} \circ \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \right)_0 = \sum_{i,k} \vec{e}_i \circ \vec{e}_k S_{ik} = \sum_{i,k} \vec{e}_i \circ \vec{e}_k \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_k}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_k} \right)_0 \quad (9)$$

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- Tensor $\vec{\vec{S}}$ has 6 independent components
- The 3 diagonal components stand for the relative change of length along x-, y- and z-directions:

$$\frac{\Delta x}{x} = S_{11} \quad \frac{\Delta y}{y} = S_{22} \quad \frac{\Delta z}{z} = S_{33} \quad (10)$$

- The relative change of volume due to a strain calculates as the sum of the diagonal components:

$$\frac{\Delta V}{V} = S_{11} + S_{22} + S_{33} = \sum_i S_{ii} = Tr \vec{\vec{S}} \quad (11)$$

- The Trace $Tr \vec{\vec{S}}$ is independent of the SoC.
- Taking eq. (9) for i=k (trace components) we get:

$$Tr \vec{\vec{S}} = \sum_i \vec{e}_i \vec{e}_i \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_i} \right)_0 = \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_i} \right)_0 = \left(\frac{\partial \vec{s}}{\partial \vec{r}} \right)_0 = div \vec{s} \quad (12)$$

whereby \vec{s} stands for the displacement vector (ref. to eq. (1))

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- The 3 non-diagonal components characterise the position of the tensor ellipsoid in the SoC

- For subscripts $l \neq k$ we have*): $S_{ik} = \bar{e}_i S \bar{e}_k = \bar{e}_i \bar{e}'_k = \bar{e}'_i \bar{e}_k$ (13)

- After some calculation it follows (as approximation):

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{12} &= \frac{\alpha_{12}}{2} = S_{21} = \frac{\alpha_{21}}{2}, & S_{13} &= \frac{\beta_{13}}{2} = S_{31} = \frac{\beta_{31}}{2}, & S_{23} &= \frac{\gamma_{23}}{2} = S_{32} = \frac{\gamma_{32}}{2} \\
 S_{12} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial s_x}{\partial y} \right), & S_{13} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_z}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial s_x}{\partial z} \right), & S_{23} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_z}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial s_y}{\partial z} \right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{14}$$

The non-diagonal strain components represent one half of the angles between the 'old and new' directions (i.e. before and after distortion) – see left

*) Note: vectores \bar{e}'_k, \bar{e}'_i are not unit vectors anymore!

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- Usually the strain tensor components are denoted with one subscript (Voigt's Notation /2/) instead of two – to shorten the expressions.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 S_{11} & S_{22} & S_{33} & S_{12} = S_{21} & S_{13} = S_{31} & S_{23} = S_{32} \\
 \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow \\
 S_1 & S_2 & S_3 & \frac{S_6}{2} & \frac{S_5}{2} & \frac{S_4}{2}
 \end{array} \tag{15}$$

2. Stress and Elasticity

- The stress of a body is defined via the substitute forces $d\vec{F}$ that maintain exactly the present deformation state (at the 'cutting' surfaces at point \vec{r})

$$d\vec{F} = d\vec{F}(\vec{r}, d\vec{A}) = d\vec{A} \vec{\vec{T}}(\vec{r}) \tag{16}$$

$$\vec{\vec{T}} = \sum_{i,k} \vec{e}_i \circ \vec{e}_k T_{ik} \tag{17}$$

with $\vec{\vec{T}}$ being the stress tensor.

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- The stress tensor is a symmetric tensor of 2nd rank (see also later)

$$\vec{T} = \vec{T}^T \quad T_{ik} = T_{ki} \quad (18)$$

and its components have the following meaning:

T_{ik} ($i=k$) are denoted as the normal stresses

T_{ik} ($i \neq k$) are denoted as the tangential stresses

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Likewise as the strains, the stress tensor's components are denoted with one subscript (Voigt's Notation /2/) instead of two – to shorten the expressions.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc}
 T_{11} & T_{22} & T_{33} & T_{12} = T_{21} & T_{13} = T_{31} & T_{23} = T_{32} \\
 \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow & \Downarrow \\
 T_1 & T_2 & T_3 & T_6 & T_5 & T_4
 \end{array} \tag{19}$$

3. Hook's Law / Elastostatics / Energy

- Hooke's Law describes the linear and unique relation between Stress and Strain:

$$T_{ik} = \sum_{l,m} c_{iklm} S_{lm} \Leftrightarrow T_{\rho} = \sum_{\sigma} c_{\rho\sigma} S_{\sigma} \quad (\text{in Voigt's Notation } \rho, \sigma: 1 \dots 6) \tag{20}$$

- Shorter *):

$$T_{ik} = c_{iklm} S_{lm} \Leftrightarrow T_{\rho} = c_{\rho\sigma} S_{\sigma}$$

Note 1: $c_{iklm}, c_{\rho\sigma}$ are the so called elastic stiffness coefficients

Note 2: Hooke's Law is typically named to be the linear relation between \vec{T} and \vec{S} , whereby non-linear terms (of \vec{S}) can be added. This is not in the focus here.

*) Note: It has to be summed up if subscripts appear several times in one expression

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- Since $\vec{\gamma}$ and $\vec{\sigma}$ are symmetric tensors, the tensor of the elastic stiffness $C_{\rho\sigma}$ has at maximum 21 independent components, when taking into account the tensor's symmetry $C_{\rho\sigma} = C_{\sigma\rho}$ (21)
- Crystals with lowest symmetry (triclinic) do have those 21 coefficients.
- Elastic coefficients for all crystallographic Point Groups (PGs) are listed in respective textbooks (e.g. /2/).

- Furthermore the invers of eq. (20) is also valid, namely

$$S_{ik} = (C_{iklm})^{-1} T_{lm} \quad S_{\rho} = (C_{\rho\sigma})^{-1} T_{\sigma} \quad (22)$$

- It has to be noticed that $(C_{\rho\sigma})^{-1}$ means the inverse stiffness tensor component, denominated as the elastic compliance^{*)} tensor component:

$$S_{\rho\sigma} = (C_{\rho\sigma})^{-1} \quad (23)$$

Note: The conversion from stiffness to compliance requires the calculation of the complete tensor inversion.

^{*)} Note: The elastic compliance- and the elastic stiffness tensors exhibit the same symmetry.

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Static Equilibrium Conditions

1. Forces:

The sum of all acting forces has to be zero.

$$\iiint \vec{f} dV + \oint \vec{T} d\vec{A} = 0 \quad (24)$$

\vec{f} is the density of the external volume forces, and $\vec{T} d\vec{A}$ are the area-proportional forces.

This can be reformed to be:

$$\vec{f} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \vec{T} = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad f_l + T_{lk,k} = 0 \quad (25)$$

2. Torques:

The sum of all acting torques has to be zero.

$$\iiint dV \vec{r} \times \vec{f} - \oint d\vec{A} \vec{T} \times \vec{r} = 0 \quad (26)$$

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Reforming of eq. (26) leads to *):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \vec{T} \times \vec{r} = 0 \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} e_k \varepsilon_{klm} T_{il} x_m = 0 \quad (27)$$

Finally the equilibrium of the torques results in the symmetry of the stress tensor (see e.g. /1/). It arises:

$$\vec{T} = \vec{T}^T \quad T_{ik} = T_{ki} \quad (28)$$

Energy of Elastic Continua

- As shown in respective textbooks (e.g. /1/) the elastic energy density η can be easily written in Voigt's Notation ***) (making use of eqs. (20) & (23)):

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} S_{\rho} c_{\rho\sigma} S_{\sigma} = \frac{1}{2} S_{\rho} T_{\rho} = \frac{1}{2} T_{\rho} S_{\rho\sigma} T_{\sigma} \quad (29)$$

*) Note: Arrows indicate the targets of the action of the differential operators

**) Note: It has to be summed up if subscripts appear several times in one expression

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- The elastic coefficients are now calculated as the 2nd derivatives:

$$c_{iklm} = \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial S_{ik} \partial S_{lm}} \Leftrightarrow c_{\rho\sigma} = \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial S_{\rho} \partial S_{\sigma}} \quad \text{and} \quad s_{iklm} = \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial T_{ik} \partial T_{lm}} \Leftrightarrow s_{\rho\sigma} = \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial T_{\rho} \partial T_{\sigma}} \quad (30)$$

- Comment: for the elastic stiffness components applies:

$$c_{\lambda\mu} = c_{ijkl} \quad (ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 1 \dots 6; \quad kl \leftrightarrow \mu = 1 \dots 6) \quad (30a)$$

and for the elastic compliance components applies:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{\lambda\mu} &= s_{ijkl} \quad (ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 1,2,3; \quad kl \leftrightarrow \mu = 1,2,3) \\ s_{\lambda\mu} &= 2s_{ijkl} \quad (ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 1,2,3; \quad kl \leftrightarrow \mu = 4,5,6) \\ s_{\lambda\mu} &= 2s_{ijkl} \quad (ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 4,5,6; \quad kl \leftrightarrow \mu = 1,2,3) \\ s_{\lambda\mu} &= 4s_{ijkl} \quad (ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 4,5,6; \quad kl \leftrightarrow \mu = 4,5,6) \end{aligned} \quad (30b)$$

4. Applications (selection)

a: Uniform Compression

- If a pure hydrostatic pressure p acts on a surface of a body then these *compression* forces are directed anti-parallel^{*)} with respect to the normal vectors \vec{n} , characterising the surface

^{*)} Note: In case of a uniform *expansion* the directions will be parallel (minus sign turns into plus sign)

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- The related boundary condition can be formulated like:

$$\vec{T}\vec{n} = -p\vec{n} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad T_{ij}n_j = -pn_i \quad (31)$$

- This can be satisfied by:

$$\vec{T} = -p\vec{E} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad T_{ij} = -p\delta_{ij} \quad (32)$$

Comment: \vec{E} is the unit tensor (symbolically: $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$) and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker Symbol, providing the values: '1' if $i=j$ and '0' if $i \neq k$.

- Turning now to the strains:

$$\vec{S} = \vec{s}\vec{T} = -\vec{s}p\vec{E} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad S_{ij} = s_{ijkl}T_{kl} = -s_{ijkl}p\delta_{kl} \quad (33)$$

- From eq. (33) follows: $S_{ij} = -s_{ijkk}p$ with $k=1,2,3$ (34)

- The elastic compliances s_{ijkk} (i.e. the Compressibility Coefficients) for all the crystallographic classes can be easily calculated or simply looked up in /2/.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

b: Uniaxial Extension

- A rod with an unchanging (but arbitrary) cross-section (of area A) along the length shall experience uniformly distributed tensile forces $T \cdot A$ at the ends.
- Having a unit vector \vec{q} ($|\vec{q}|=1$) along the rod axis, the stress tensors reads:

$$\vec{T} = T\vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad T_{ij} = Tq_i q_j \quad (35)$$

- For the resulting strain parallel to direction of \vec{q} follows:

$$\vec{S} = T\vec{s}\vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad S_{ij} = Ts_{ijkl}q_k q_l \quad (36)$$

- The elongation of the rod along \vec{q} can be obtained:

$$\frac{\Delta l}{l} = S_{ij}q_i q_j = Ts_{ijkl}q_i q_j q_k q_l \quad (37)$$

- The expression:

$$E^{-1}(\vec{q}) = s_{ijkl}q_i q_j q_k q_l \quad (38)$$

is called the reciprocal Young's Modulus for direction \vec{q}

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Comment: Vector \vec{q} ($|\vec{q}|=1$) can be depicted as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 q_x &= q_1 = |\vec{q}| \cdot |\vec{e}_x| \cdot \cos(\vec{q}, \vec{e}_x) = \cos(\alpha) \\
 q_y &= q_2 = |\vec{q}| \cdot |\vec{e}_y| \cdot \cos(\vec{q}, \vec{e}_y) = \cos(\beta) \\
 q_z &= q_3 = |\vec{q}| \cdot |\vec{e}_z| \cdot \cos(\vec{q}, \vec{e}_z) = \cos(\gamma)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{39}$$

- To ease laborious calculations of eq. (38) Voigt's Notation will be useful:

$$q_i q_j = (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_\lambda \tag{40}$$

with $i, j \rightarrow \lambda$ acc. to : 11 \rightarrow 1; 22 \rightarrow 2; 33 \rightarrow 3; 12 \rightarrow 6; 13 \rightarrow 5; 23 \rightarrow 4

- Rewriting stress and strain (ref. to eqs. (35), (36)) this yields*):

$$T_\mu = T (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_\mu \quad \text{and} \quad S_\lambda = T s_{\lambda\sigma} (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_\sigma \tag{41}$$

*) Note: The expression $\vec{q} \circ \vec{q}$ is called dyad and represents a tensor, not a scalar product!

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- Finally the reciprocal Young's Modulus can be expressed. It is listed for the crystallographic classes e.g. in /2/.

$$E^{-1}(\vec{q}) = s_{\lambda\mu} (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_{\lambda} (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_{\mu} \quad (42)$$

c: Shear

- Let's have a rectangular rod with uniformly distributed tangential forces to the side faces. The rod shall be in equilibrium of forces.
- \vec{q} shall be a unit vector normal to the glide-planes and \vec{p} a unit vector toward the glide-direction (e.g. ref. to eqs. (18), (19), and the pic there). Both vectors shall be mutually perpendicular.

$$\vec{T} = T(\vec{p} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{p}) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad T_{ij} = T(p_i q_j + q_i p_j) \quad (43)$$

- Now the strain can be expressed*):

$$\vec{S} = 2T\vec{s}(\vec{p} \circ \vec{q}) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad S_{ij} = 2Ts_{ijkl} p_k q_l \quad (44)$$

*) Note: Factor 2 in eq. (44) originates from the fact that it holds: $\vec{p} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{p} = 2 \vec{p} \circ \vec{q}$ (because of the symmetry of S_{ijkl} regarding subscripts k and l)

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- Similar to eq. (37) the following shear component of $\vec{\vec{S}}$ is of interest:

$$\vec{p} \circ \vec{\vec{S}} \circ \vec{q} = 2T (\vec{p} \circ \vec{q}) \circ \vec{\vec{S}} \circ (\vec{p} \circ \vec{q}) = 2Ts_{ijkl} p_i q_j p_k q_l = \frac{\tau}{2} \quad (45)$$

with τ being the shear-angle, and use has been made of eqs. (13),(14)

- From eq. (45) the Shear Modulus is given:

$$G^{-1}(\vec{p}, \vec{q}) \equiv 4(\vec{p} \circ \vec{q}) \circ \vec{\vec{S}} \circ (\vec{p} \circ \vec{q}) = 4s_{ijkl} p_i q_j p_k q_l = \frac{\tau}{T} \quad (46)$$

which reads in Voigt's Notation:

$$G^{-1}(\vec{p}, \vec{q}) = s_{\lambda\mu} (\vec{p} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{p})_{\lambda} (\vec{p} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{p})_{\mu} = \frac{\tau}{T} \quad (47)$$

where $(\vec{p} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{p})_{\lambda} = (p_i q_j + q_i p_j)$ $ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 1, \dots, 6$ (48)

Comment: It is worth to mention (/2/) that:

- The Shear Modulus is symmetric: $G^{-1}(\vec{p}, \vec{q}) = G^{-1}(\vec{q}, \vec{p})$
- Anisotropic bodies experience volume changes under shear stresses.

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d: Bending of Rods

- Let's assume a rectangular rod (length: c , width: $2a$, thickness: $2b$, with $c \gg a, b$), fixed on its left side.

- The vectors $\vec{m}, \vec{n}, \vec{q}$ are unit vectors and belong to the special (non-crystal-physical), but orthonormal SoC $(X_1' X_2' X_3')$
- The bending moment (torque) \vec{M}_0 is created by an external force \vec{F}_0 applied at the end ($x_3' = c$): $\vec{M}_0 = c\vec{q} \times \vec{F}_0 = -cF_0\vec{n}$ (49)
- The equilibrium condition for the torques demands that the sum of the 'replacement torque' \vec{M}_S (which is uniform along axis X_3') and the externally applied \vec{M}_0 (also not depending on X_3') must be zero)

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$$\boxed{\vec{M}_0 + \vec{M}_S = 0} \quad (50)$$

- Assuming forces (per unit area) across the rod's cross section S like:

$$\vec{F}_S = \vec{T}' = -kx_1' \vec{q} \quad (51)$$

we get:

$$\vec{M}_S = \iint_S x_1' \vec{m} \times \vec{F}_S dS = - \int_{-a-b}^{+a+b} \int x_1' \vec{m} \times kx_1' \vec{q} dx_1' dx_2' = \frac{4}{3} ab^3 k \vec{n}$$

and on the other hand:

$$\vec{M}_0 = c\vec{q} \times \vec{F}_0 = -cF_0 \vec{n}$$

- With eq. (50): $\left(-F_0 c + \frac{4}{3} ab^3 k\right) \vec{n} = \vec{0}$ we obtain $k = \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3}$ (52)

- Eq. (52) expresses the boundary conditions regarding the torques at the rod's ends $x_3' = 0, x_3' = c$

$$\vec{T}' (\pm \vec{q}) = \pm \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} x_1' \vec{q}$$

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- Yielding a stress tensor like:

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{3F_0c}{4ab^3} x_1' (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q}) \quad (53)$$

- In the special SoC only one component is non-zero:

$$T'_{33} = \frac{3F_0c}{4ab^3} x_1' = T'_3 \quad (54)$$

- With Hooke's Law follows:

$$S'_{ik} = s'_{ik33} T'_{33} \rightarrow S'_{\lambda} = s'_{\lambda 3} T'_3 = s'_{\lambda 3} \frac{3F_0c}{4ab^3} x_1' \quad (55)$$

- That strain results in a gradual bending of the rod along axis which can be easily described by a rotation angle $\varphi_2' (x_3')$ around X_2' whereby (accord. to eq. (6)):

$$\vec{\varphi} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \vec{r}} \times \vec{s} \right)_0 = \frac{1}{2} (rot \vec{s})_0 \quad \text{and in components} \quad \varphi_i = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial x_m} \quad (56)$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- To calculate $\frac{\partial \varphi_2'}{\partial x_3'}$ we use the formulae:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j'} \varphi_i' = \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_m'} S_{nj}' = (\text{rot} \vec{S}')_{ij} \quad (57)$$

Proof:

With eq. (56) we start with
$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j'} \varphi_i' = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j'} \left(\frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial s_n'}{\partial x_m'} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial^2 s_n'}{\partial x_j' \partial x_m'} = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial^2 s_n'}{\partial x_j' \partial x_m'} + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial^2 s_j'}{\partial x_n' \partial x_m'}$$

whereby the last term, which has been arbitrarily added, is identical to zero and therefore no mistake. Summarizing the expression and using definition of eq. (9) leads to:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j'} \varphi_i' = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial^2 s_n'}{\partial x_j' \partial x_m'} + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial^2 s_j'}{\partial x_n' \partial x_m'} = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_m'} \left(\frac{\partial s_n'}{\partial x_j'} + \frac{\partial s_j'}{\partial x_n'} \right) = \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_m'} S_{nj}'$$

Finally we verify eq. (57):
$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j'} \varphi_i' = \varepsilon_{imn} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_m'} S_{nj}' = (\text{rot} \vec{S}')_{ij}$$

Comment:

It has to be carefully distinguished between \vec{s}' (displacement vector) and \vec{S}' (strain tensor)

The apostrophes always indicate that the given quantities are referred to the special SoC which does not necessarily coincide with the crystal-physical SoC.

Elastic coefficients as listed in the textbooks are referred to the respective crystal-physical SoCs and may need to be transformed according to current application.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Execution of eq. (57) results in:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_2'}{\partial x_3'} = \varepsilon_{231} \frac{\partial S_{13}'}{\partial x_3'} + \varepsilon_{213} \frac{\partial S_{33}'}{\partial x_1'} = \frac{\partial S_{13}'}{\partial x_3'} - \frac{\partial S_{33}'}{\partial x_1'} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S_5'}{\partial x_3'} - \frac{\partial S_3'}{\partial x_1'} \quad (58)$$

- with eq. (55) follows:

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S_5'}{\partial x_3'} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial S_3'}{\partial x_1'} = -s_{33}' \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} \quad (59)$$

and finally we get:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_2'}{\partial x_3'} = -s_{33}' \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} \quad (60)$$

- Next step is the calculation of the dependence $\varphi_2'(x_3')$

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_2'(x_3') &= \int d\varphi_2' = - \int s_{33}' \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} dx_3' \\ \varphi_2'(x_3') &= -s_{33}' \frac{3F_0 c x_3'}{4ab^3} + C \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

- Constant C equals to zero, because $\varphi_2'(x_3' = 0)$ must be zero

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Having now the bending angle φ_2' of the rod we can calculate the maximum deviation (I_{X_1}') of the rod from axis X_3' at position $X_3' = c$
- Angle φ_2' is defined like:

$$\varphi_2' \approx \frac{\Delta X_1'}{\Delta X_3'} = \frac{dx_1'}{dx_3'}$$

- Therefore we finally have:

$$I_{X_1}' = X_1'(X_3' = c) = \int_0^c \varphi_2'(X_3') dx_3' = -\frac{3F_0 s_{33}' c^3}{8ab^3} = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3 E} \quad (62)$$

with $s_{33}' = E^{-1}$ (reciprocal Young's Modulus) along the rod axis (see also eqs. (38, 42)) - within the special SoC.

Note 1: The arrangement of the special SoC (meaning: "how the crystal rod is cut") in relation to the crystal-physical SoC might require certain transformations of the elastic coefficients, which have been described in previous sections (e.g. eqs. (38-42)).

Note 2: Above made considerations also apply to other rod cross sections – just eqs. (51,52) need to be adjusted.

Note 3: The body's material is extended above the neutral plane (see pic.) and compressed underneath.

Note 4: The body's volume doesn't change during bending.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

Question: Are there other deformations when an anisotropic rod is bent?

- Similar like in the preceding considerations of this chapter we have to check the twisting angls as function of X_3' :

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_3'}{\partial X_3'} = \varepsilon_{312} \frac{\partial S'_{23}}{\partial X_1'} + \varepsilon_{321} \frac{\partial S'_{13}}{\partial X_2'} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S'_4}{\partial X_1'} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S'_5}{\partial X_2'} \quad (63)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_1'}{\partial X_3'} = \varepsilon_{123} \frac{\partial S'_{33}}{\partial X_2'} + \varepsilon_{132} \frac{\partial S'_{23}}{\partial X_3'} = \frac{\partial S'_3}{\partial X_2'} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S'_4}{\partial X_3'} \quad (64)$$

- With eq. (55) we get : $\varphi_3'(x_3') = s'_{34} \frac{3F_0 c}{8ab^3} x_3'$ and $\varphi_1'(x_3') = 0$

$$\rightarrow I_{X_1'} = x_1'(x_3' = c) = \int_{-b}^b \varphi_3(x_3' = c) dx_1' = \frac{3F_0 s'_{34} c^2}{4ab^2} \quad (65)$$

$$\rightarrow I_{X_2'} = x_2'(x_3' = c) = \int_{-a}^a \varphi_3(x_3' = c) dx_2' = \frac{3F_0 s'_{34} c^2}{4b^3} \quad (66)$$

- No further twisting nor bending elsewhere

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

Answer: Yes, there are more deformations – in particular twisting around the rod's axis! Not happens to isotropic bodies!

- The responsible elastic coefficient within the special SoC can be expressed by the tabulated elastic constants (which refer to the crystal-physical SoC):

$$s'_{34} = 2s'_{3332} = 2(\vec{q} \circ \vec{q}) \overset{\equiv}{s}(\vec{q} \circ \vec{n}) \quad (67)$$

- And for eq. (65) follows:

$$I_{X_1'} = \frac{3F_0 c^2}{2ab^2} s_{ijkl} q_i q_j q_k n_l \quad (68)$$

Comment:

The q_i, q_j, q_k, n_l denote the projections (cosines) of vectors \vec{q} and \vec{n} onto the directions of the respective crystal-physical SoC, as shown in eq. (39).

- Even more compact eq. (68) reads:

$$I_{X_1'} = \frac{3F_0 c^2}{2ab^2} s_{\lambda\mu} (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_\lambda (\vec{q} \circ \vec{n} + \vec{n} \circ \vec{q})_\mu \quad (69)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{q} \circ \vec{q})_\lambda &= q_i q_j (ij \leftrightarrow \lambda = 1, \dots, 6) \\ (\vec{q} \circ \vec{n} + \vec{n} \circ \vec{q})_\mu &= q_k n_l + n_k q_l (kl \leftrightarrow \mu = 1, \dots, 6) \end{aligned}$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

e: Torsion of Rods

- Let's assume a round rod (length: l , radius: R) with $l > R$, fixed on its lower side.

- Beside the special (non-crystal-physical) SoC $(\vec{m}, \vec{n}, \vec{q})$ we introduce a local SoC $(\vec{e}_r, \vec{e}_\varphi, \vec{q})$ at each point of the rod
- The relationship between both systems writes:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1' &= r \cos \varphi \\ x_2' &= r \sin \varphi \\ x_3' &= x_3 \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

- The torsion moment (torque) \vec{M} is created by an external force per unit area $\vec{F} = kr\vec{e}_\varphi$ applied at the end of the rod $x_3' = l$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Calculating the torque we get:

$$\vec{M} = \iint_S \vec{r} \times \vec{F} dS = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^R r \vec{e}_r \times k r \vec{e}_\varphi r dr d\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \pi R^4 k \vec{q}$$

with:

$$k = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} \quad (71)$$

- The boundary conditions can be expressed as follows:

$$\vec{T}' \cdot \vec{e}_r = 0 \quad \rightarrow \text{no forces on the lateral surface of the rod} \\ \text{and} \quad (72)$$

$$\vec{T}' \cdot \vec{q} = \left(\frac{2M}{\pi R^4} \right) r \vec{e}_\varphi \quad \rightarrow \text{only forces on the end-surface of the rod}$$

and are satisfied by the stress tensor:

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} r (\vec{e}_\varphi \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{e}_\varphi) \quad (73)$$

- $r \vec{e}_\varphi$ shall be now expressed in terms of the special (Cartesian) SoC

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Acc. to the pic above we can write:

$$\vec{r} = r\vec{e}_r = x_1'\vec{m} + x_2'\vec{n} \quad \text{with} \quad r = \sqrt{x_1'^2 + x_2'^2} \quad (74)$$

- $r\vec{e}_\varphi$ stands perpendicular to \vec{q} and $\vec{e}_r \rightarrow$

$$r\vec{e}_\varphi = \vec{q} \times \vec{e}_r r = \begin{vmatrix} \vec{m} & \vec{n} & \vec{q} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ x_1' & x_2' & 0 \end{vmatrix} = -x_2'\vec{m} + x_1'\vec{n} \quad (75)$$

- With eq. (73) we get:

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} [(x_1'\vec{n} - x_2'\vec{m}) \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ (x_1'\vec{n} - x_2'\vec{m})] \quad (76)$$

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} [x_1'(\vec{n} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{n}) - x_2'(\vec{m} \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{m})]$$

- Introducing the following indexation for the special SoC:

$$\vec{m} \leftrightarrow 1, \quad \vec{n} \leftrightarrow 2, \quad \vec{q} \leftrightarrow 3$$

leads to

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} \left[x_1' \left[\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right] - x_2' \left[\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right] \right] \quad (77)$$

and finally to:

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -x_2' \\ 0 & 0 & x_1' \\ -x_2' & x_1' & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (78)$$

- Now we can write down all the strains within the special SoC

$$\begin{aligned} S_1' &= s_{15}' T_5' + s_{14}' T_4' & \rightarrow & S_1' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-s_{15}' x_2' + s_{14}' x_1') \\ S_2' &= s_{25}' T_5' + s_{24}' T_4' & \rightarrow & S_2' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-s_{25}' x_2' + s_{24}' x_1') \\ S_3' &= s_{35}' T_5' + s_{34}' T_4' & \rightarrow & S_3' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-s_{35}' x_2' + s_{34}' x_1') \\ S_4' &= s_{45}' T_5' + s_{44}' T_4' & \rightarrow & S_4' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-s_{45}' x_2' + s_{44}' x_1') \\ S_5' &= s_{55}' T_5' + s_{54}' T_4' & \rightarrow & S_5' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-s_{55}' x_2' + s_{54}' x_1') \\ S_6' &= s_{65}' T_5' + s_{64}' T_4' & \rightarrow & S_6' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-s_{65}' x_2' + s_{64}' x_1') \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- The axial torsion (per unit length) g'_3 is acc. to eq. (57) defined as:

$$g'_3 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_3} \varphi'_3 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_1} S'_{23} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_2} S'_{13} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'_1} S'_4 - \frac{\partial}{\partial x'_2} S'_5 \right) \quad (80)$$

and results together with eq. (79) in:
$$g'_3 = \frac{M}{\pi R^4} (s'_{44} + s'_{55}) \quad (81)$$

Comment: Other contributions from eq. (79) are not valid because of eq. (80)

- Next step is the calculation of the dependence $\varphi'_3(x'_3)$

$$\varphi'_3(x'_3) = \int d\varphi'_3 = \int (s'_{44} + s'_{55}) \frac{M}{\pi R^4} dx'_3 \quad (82)$$

$$\varphi'_3(x'_3) = \frac{M}{\pi R^4} (s'_{44} + s'_{55}) x'_3 + C$$

- Constant C equals to zero, because $\varphi'_3(x'_3 = 0)$ must be zero

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Having now the torsion angle $\varphi_3'(x_3')$ we have the maximum torsion angle $\varphi_3'(x_3' = l)$ of the rod around axis X_3'

$$\varphi_3'(x_3' = l) = \frac{M \cdot l}{\pi R^4 (s'_{44} + s'_{55})} \Leftrightarrow M = \frac{\pi R^4}{l (s'_{44} + s'_{55})} \cdot \varphi_3'(x_3' = l) = \frac{C}{l} \cdot \varphi_3'(x_3' = l) \quad (83)^1$$

- Eq. (83) is valid within the special SoC.
- Rewriting the elastic compliances yield:

$$(s'_{44} + s'_{55}) = 4(s'_{2323} + s'_{1313}) = 4(s'_{2323} + s'_{1313} + s'_{3333} - s'_{3333}) = 4(s'_{k3k3} - s'_{3333})$$

- This expression still refers to the special SoC. Using the direction cosines of the rod's vector \vec{q} it can be referred to the crystal-physical SoC (see eq.(39)).

$$4(s_{k_j k_l} q_j q_l - s_{ijkl} q_i q_j q_k q_l) = 4(s_{ijkl} (\delta_{ik} - q_i q_k) q_j q_l) \quad (84)$$

Note 1: Quantity C is called the torsion stiffness of the rod. This is the formula to be used to calculate $[s'_{44} + s'_{55}]$ in experiments.

Note 2: The arrangement of the special SoC (meaning: "how the crystal rod is cut") in relation to the crystal-physical SoC might require certain transformations of the elastic coefficients, which have been described in previous sections .

Note 3: Above made considerations do not apply to other rod cross sections.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- With eq. (84) C can be written now:

$$C(\vec{q}) = \frac{\pi R^4}{4(s_{ijkl}(\delta_{ik} - q_i q_k)q_j q_l)}$$

- Further we obtain:

$$G(\vec{q}) = \frac{2 \cdot C(\vec{q})}{\pi R^4} = \frac{1}{2(s_{ijkl}(\delta_{ik} - q_i q_k)q_j q_l)} \quad (85)$$

and

$$G^{-1}(\vec{q}) = 2\left(\vec{q} \circ \vec{Z} \circ \vec{q} - E^{-1}(\vec{q})\right)$$

This is called *the reciprocal of the shear modulus* and can be found tabulated for the crystallographic classes e.g. in /2/

Question: Are there other deformations when an anisotropic rod is twisted?

-

Similar like in the preceding considerations (eqs. (57,80)) we have to check whether it bends around axis X'_1 respectively X'_2 . With eq. (79) we get:

$$g'_1 = \frac{\partial \varphi'_1}{\partial X'_3} = \varepsilon_{123} \frac{\partial S'_{33}}{\partial X'_2} + \varepsilon_{132} \frac{\partial S'_{23}}{\partial X'_3} = \frac{\partial S'_3}{\partial X'_2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S'_4}{\partial X'_3} = -\frac{2M}{\pi R^4} S'_{35}$$

$$g'_2 = \frac{\partial \varphi'_2}{\partial X'_3} = \varepsilon_{231} \frac{\partial S'_{13}}{\partial X'_3} + \varepsilon_{213} \frac{\partial S'_{33}}{\partial X'_1} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial S'_5}{\partial X'_3} - \frac{\partial S'_3}{\partial X'_1} = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} S'_{34} \quad (86)$$

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- There is an axis of bend parallel to $s'_{35}\vec{m} + s'_{34}\vec{n}$ with a magnitude of

$$g' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} \sqrt{(s'_{35})^2 + (s'_{34})^2} \quad (87)$$

- The radikand can be rewritten to be:

$$(s'_{35}{}^2 + s'_{34}{}^2) = 4(s'_{3313}s'_{3313} + s'_{3323}s'_{3323} + s'_{3333}s'_{3333} - s'_{3333}s'_{3333}) = 4(s'_{33k3}s'_{33k3} - s'_{3333}s'_{3333})$$

followed by the transformation to the crystal physical SoC which yields:

$$4(s'_{33k3}s'_{33k3} - s'_{3333}s'_{3333}) = 4(s_{ijkl}q_i q_j q_l \cdot s_{ijkl}q_i q_j q_l - s_{ijkl}q_i q_j q_k q_l \cdot s_{ijkl}q_i q_j q_k q_l)$$

- This expression can be shortened, thus finally we have:

$$\vartheta' = \frac{4M}{\pi R^4} \sqrt{\vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{s} \cdot \vec{s} \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} - \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{s} \cdot \vec{s} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q}}$$

$$\vartheta' = \frac{4M}{\pi R^4} \sqrt{\vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{s} \cdot (I - \vec{q} \circ \vec{q}) \cdot \vec{s} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q} \circ \vec{q}}$$

Answer: Yes, there are more deformations – in particular bending around the rod's axes perpendicular to torsion axis! Not happens to isotropic bodies!

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Let's now focus on rods with an arbitrary cross-section, fixed on its lower side. Details can be found in the literature (e.g. /8/,/9/)
- For sake of better illustration we use (in the beginning) the same pic as done for rods with circular cross-section.

- We have the special (non-crystal-physical) SoC $(\vec{m}, \vec{n}, \vec{q})$

- The torsion angle per length is constant and calculates:

$$g'_3 = \frac{d\varphi'_3}{dl} \Rightarrow \varphi'_3(x'_3) = g'_3 \cdot x'_3 \quad (88)$$

- The displacements vector varies along the rod's axis:

$$\vec{s}' = \varphi'_3(x'_3) \cdot \vec{q} \times \vec{r}$$

- The radius vector is represented by:

$$\vec{r} = x'_1 \vec{m} + x'_2 \vec{n} \quad \text{with} \quad r = \sqrt{x'^2_1 + x'^2_2}$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Calculation of the displacement yields:

$$\vec{s}' = \begin{vmatrix} \vec{m} & \vec{n} & \vec{q} \\ 0 & 0 & \varphi_3'(x_3') \\ x_1' & x_2' & 0 \end{vmatrix} = -x_2' \cdot \varphi_3'(x_3') \cdot \vec{m} + x_1' \cdot \varphi_3'(x_3') \cdot \vec{n} \quad (89)$$

- It has to be considered that - in general - every cross-section plane along the rod's axis can become, as a result of the torsion, curved, i.e. is not planar anymore.
- Therefore the so called 'torsion function' ξ has to be added to eq. (89) and we get

$$\vec{s}' = -x_2' \cdot \varphi_3'(x_3') \cdot \vec{m} + x_1' \cdot \varphi_3'(x_3') \cdot \vec{n} + g_3 \cdot \xi(x_1', x_2') \cdot \vec{q} \quad (90)$$

- Next step is the calculation of the strain tensor components. According to eqs. (9,14) we obtain:

$$S_{ik} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial s_k}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_k} \right) \Rightarrow S_{13} = \frac{g_3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1'} - x_2' \right) \quad \text{and} \quad S_{23} = \frac{g_3}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_2'} + x_1' \right) \quad (91)$$

- All other strains are identical to zero.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Next step is the calculation of the resulting stress components, according to Hooke's Law (see eq. (20)): $T'_{ik} = c'_{iklm} S'_{lm}$

$$\Rightarrow T'_{13} = 2c'_{1313}S'_{13} + 2c'_{1323}S'_{23} = g'_3 \left(c'_{1313} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) + c'_{1323} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow T'_{23} = 2c'_{2313}S'_{13} + 2c'_{2323}S'_{23} = g'_3 \left(c'_{2313} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) + c'_{2323} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow T'_{ik} = 2c'_{ik13}S'_{13} + 2c'_{ik23}S'_{23} = g'_3 \left(c'_{ik13} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) + c'_{ik23} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \right) \text{ with } i, k = 1, 2, 3$$

- In Voigt's Notation this reads: $T'_i = c'_{im} S'_m$

$$\Rightarrow T'_5 = c'_{55}S'_5 + c'_{54}S'_4 = g'_3 \left(c'_{55} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) + c'_{54} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow T'_4 = c'_{45}S'_5 + c'_{44}S'_4 = g'_3 \left(c'_{45} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) + c'_{44} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow T'_m = c'_{m5}S'_5 + c'_{m4}S'_4 = g'_3 \left(c'_{m5} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) + c'_{m4} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \right) \text{ with } m = 1, 2, 3, 6$$

(92)

- Within the current formalism we have to stipulate that only certain stresses and strains are present (here exclusively T'_4, T'_5, S'_4, S'_5).
- Therefore we have to demand that in the special SoC following elastic coefficients are identical to zero: $c'_{14}, c'_{24}, c'_{34}, c'_{54}, c'_{64}, c'_{15}, c'_{25}, c'_{35}, c'_{65}$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- If the special SoC and the crystal-physical SoC coincide, this is NOT(!) the case for the Point Groups (PGs): triclinic, monoclinic, and trigonal /2/.
- In other cases – when the SoCs don't coincide - the elastic coefficients of the crystal-physical SoC have to be transferred into the special SoC – reflecting the orientation of the rod as cut. If then, in the special SoC, the above mentioned coefficients are not equal to zero (or at least very small), the forthcoming formalism doesn't apply precisely.
- Now we introduce the auxiliary function $\chi(x'_1, x'_2)$

$$T'_5 \equiv g'_3 \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x'_2} \quad \text{and} \quad T'_4 \equiv -g'_3 \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x'_1} \quad (93)$$

- Together with eqs. (91,92) we have:

$$\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x'_2} = c'_{55} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x'_1} = -c'_{44} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \quad (94)$$

- Conversion of the equations lead to:

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} = \frac{1}{c'_{55}} \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x'_2} \right) + x'_2 \quad \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} = -\frac{1}{c'_{44}} \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x'_1} \right) - x'_1$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1^i \partial x_2^i} = \frac{1}{c_{55}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_2^{i2}} \right) + 1 \qquad \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1^i \partial x_2^i} = -\frac{1}{c_{44}} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^{i2}} \right) - 1$$

- Through formation of the difference we get the differential equation:

$$\boxed{\frac{1}{c_{55}} \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_2^{i2}} + \frac{1}{c_{44}} \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^{i2}} = -2} \qquad (95)$$

- The boundary conditions require special attention. We don't want to have forces on the lateral surface of the rod (also in accordance with the experiment):

$$dF_i = T_{ik}^i v_k^i \cdot dS \quad \text{with} \quad v_{x_3}^i = v_3^i = 0, v_{x_1}^i = v_1^i \neq 0, v_{x_2}^i = v_2^i \neq 0,$$

$$\Rightarrow T_{31}^i v_1^i + T_{32}^i v_2^i = 0 \quad \Rightarrow T_5^i v_1^i + T_4^i v_2^i = 0$$

- With eq. (93) we get:

$$g_3^i \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2^i} v_1^i - g_3^i \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1^i} v_2^i = 0 \qquad (96)$$

- Let's now focus on the vector $\vec{v}^i = v_1^i \vec{m} + v_2^i \vec{n}$ which stands perpendicular on the surface, whereby we have $v_3^i = 0, v_1^i \neq 0, v_2^i \neq 0$

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- We start with a vector along the circumference of the cross-section:

$$d\vec{l}' = dx_1' \vec{m} + dx_2' \vec{n}$$

- This vector stands always perpendicular to $\vec{v}' = v_1' \vec{m} + v_2' \vec{n}$ which yields

$$\vec{v}' \cdot d\vec{l}' = v_1' dx_1' + v_2' dx_2' = 0 \Rightarrow v_1' = -\frac{v_2' dx_2'}{dx_1'}$$

- Normalisation means $|\vec{v}'| = 1 = \sqrt{(v_1')^2 + (v_2')^2}$ and leads together with

$$(dl')^2 = (dx_1')^2 + (dx_2')^2 \quad \text{to} \quad v_1' = -\frac{dx_2'}{dl} \quad \text{and} \quad v_2' = \frac{dx_1'}{dl} \quad (97)$$

- Inserting of eq. (97) into eq. (96) we get:

$$-\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2'} \frac{dx_2'}{dl} - \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1'} \frac{dx_1'}{dl} = 0$$

- Multiplication by (-dl) leads finally to :

$$\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2'} dx_2' + \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1'} dx_1' = 0 \quad (98)$$

which equals the total differential (dχ) of the function χ

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Since $d\chi=0$ on the circumference, χ itself must be constant there.
- In the differential equation (see eq. (95)) only derivatives of χ appear, thus we can put $\chi=0$ on the circumference.
- Now we must select a specific cross-section of the rod – and we are going to choose a rectangular cross-section (view along the rod axis).

- We do have 4 boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1. \quad \chi(x'_1 = 0, x'_2) = 0 & \quad 2. \quad \chi(x'_1 = a, x'_2) = 0 \\
 3. \quad \chi(x'_1, x'_2 = -\frac{b}{2}) = 0 & \quad 4. \quad \chi(x'_1, x'_2 = \frac{b}{2}) = 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{99}$$

- Using the Fourier 'Ansatz': $\chi(x'_1, x'_2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} W_k(x'_2) \cdot \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x'_1$ the (100)
 boundary conditions in direction of X'_1 (i.e. 1. and 2.) are already fulfilled.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- We want now to set up a differential equation for the Fourier coefficients $W_k(x'_2)$

- The scalar product looks like:

$$\left\langle \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x'_1 \left| \chi(x'_1, x'_2) \right. \right\rangle = \left\langle \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x'_1 \left| \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} W_k(x'_2) \cdot \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x'_1 \right. \right\rangle$$

$$\left\langle \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x'_1 \left| \chi(x'_1, x'_2) \right. \right\rangle = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} W_k(x'_2) \left\langle \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x'_1 \left| \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x'_1 \right. \right\rangle$$

- Since $\left\langle \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x'_1 \left| \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x'_1 \right. \right\rangle = \delta_{mk} \frac{a}{2} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } k \neq m \\ \frac{a}{2} & \text{if } k = m \end{cases}$ we get:

$$\left\langle \sin \frac{m\pi}{a} x'_1 \left| \chi(x'_1, x'_2) \right. \right\rangle = W_m(x'_2) \frac{a}{2} \quad m \Leftrightarrow k \quad (101)$$

- Finally, applying the definition of the scalar product, we obtain:

$$\Rightarrow W_k(x'_2) = \frac{2}{a} \int_0^a \left(\sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x'_1 \right) \cdot \chi(x'_1, x'_2) dx'_1 \quad (102)$$

Note: To ease the scripting, until further notice the apostrophes are omitted.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- The *first integration by parts* leads to:

$$W_k(x_2) = \frac{2}{a} \left[-\frac{a}{k\pi} \cdot \cos \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \chi(x_1, x_2) \Big|_{x_1=0}^{x_1=a} + \frac{a}{k\pi} \int_0^a \cos \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \chi(x_1, x_2)}{\partial x_1} dx_1 \right]$$

- Due to the boundary conditions (see eq. (99)) the 1st term vanishes
- The *second integration by parts* leads to:

$$W_k(x_2) = \frac{2}{a} \left[\frac{a^2}{k^2 \pi^2} \cdot \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1} \Big|_{x_1=0}^{x_1=a} - \frac{a^2}{k^2 \pi^2} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^2} dx_1 \right]$$

- Again the 1st term vanishes and we have:

$$W_k(x_2) = -\frac{2a}{k^2 \pi^2} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^2} dx_1 \quad (103)$$

- The differential equation (see eq. (95)) can be reformed to be:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^2} = \left(-2 - \frac{1}{c_{55}} \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_2^2} \right) \cdot c_{44} \quad \text{and is inserted into eq. (103)} \rightarrow$$

$$W_k(x_2) = -\frac{2a}{k^2 \pi^2} \left[-\int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot 2c_{44} dx_1 - \frac{d^2}{dx_2^2} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \frac{c_{44}}{c_{55}} \chi dx_1 \right]$$

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$$W_k(x_2) = \frac{4ac_{44}}{k^2\pi^2} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot dx_1 + \frac{2ac_{44}}{c_{55}k^2\pi^2} \frac{d^2}{dx_2^2} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot \chi \cdot dx_1$$

- Acc. to eq. (101) the value of the last integral is $\frac{a}{2} W_k(x_2)$ and yields:

$$W_k(x_2) = \frac{4ac_{44}}{k^2\pi^2} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot dx_1 + \frac{a^2 c_{44}}{c_{55}k^2\pi^2} \ddot{W}_k(x_2)$$

- Further reformation finally leads to the differential equation for $W_k(x_2)$

$$\boxed{\ddot{W}_k(x_2) - \frac{c_{55}k^2\pi^2}{c_{44}a^2} W_k(x_2) = -\frac{4c_{55}}{a} \int_0^a \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \cdot dx_1} \quad (104)$$

- First we go now for the homogeneous solution of eq. (104) and use the

‘Ansatz’ $W_k(x_2) = e^{-\lambda x_2}$ and get: $\lambda = \pm \sqrt{\frac{k^2\pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}}}$

- The solution can be written down as: $W_k(x_2) = c_1 \cdot e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2\pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}}} x_2} + c_2 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2\pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}}} x_2}$

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- Now we go for the particular solution of eq. (104) and use the 'Ansatz'

$$W_k(x_2) = A$$

- Insertion into eq. (104) yields

$$-\frac{c_{55}k^2\pi^2}{a^2c_{44}}A = -\frac{4c_{55}}{a}\int_0^a \sin\frac{k\pi}{a}x_1 \cdot dx_1$$

- The integral amounts to:

$$\int_0^a \sin\frac{k\pi}{a}x_1 \cdot dx_1 = -\frac{a}{k\pi} \cos\frac{k\pi}{a}x_1 \Big|_{x_1=0}^{x_1=a} = -\frac{a}{k\pi}(\cos k\pi - 1)$$

and is unequal to zero only if $k=1,3,5,\dots$ and amounts then $\frac{2a}{k\pi}$

- Consequently we get for A: $A = \frac{8a^2c_{44}}{k^3\pi^3}$

- The general solution of the differential equation is the sum of the homogeneous and particular solutions and can be written down as:

$$W_k(x_2) = c_1 \cdot e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2\pi^2c_{55}}{a^2c_{44}}}x_2} + c_2 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2\pi^2c_{55}}{a^2c_{44}}}x_2} + \frac{8a^2c_{44}}{k^3\pi^3}$$

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- Adjustment of the solution to the boundary conditions 3. and 4. results for the constants c_1 and c_2 in:

$$0 = c_1 \cdot e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} + c_2 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} + \frac{8a^2 c_{44}}{k^3 \pi^3}$$

$$0 = c_1 \cdot e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} + c_2 e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} + \frac{8a^2 c_{44}}{k^3 \pi^3}$$

$$\Rightarrow c_1 = c_2 \equiv c = -A \cdot \frac{e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} - e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}}}{e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} - e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}}}$$

- The general solution now reads:

$$W_k(x_2) = c \cdot \left(e^{+\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} x_2}} + c_2 e^{-\sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} x_2}} \right) + A$$

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$$W_k(x_2) = A \cdot \left[\left(\frac{\sinh \sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}}{\sinh \sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} b}} \right) \cdot 2 \cosh \sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}}} x_2 + 1 \right]$$

- Making use of the identity $\sinh 2x = 2 \cdot \sinh x \cdot \cosh x$

$$W_k(x_2) = \frac{8a^2 c_{44}}{k^3 \pi^3} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{\cosh \sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}}} x_2}{\cosh \sqrt{\frac{k^2 \pi^2 c_{55}}{a^2 c_{44}} \frac{b}{2}}} \right)$$

- Finally we get with eq. (100) the auxiliary stress function to be:

$$\chi(x_1, x_2) = \frac{8a^2 c_{44}}{\pi^3} \cdot \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^3} \left(1 - \frac{\cosh \frac{k\pi}{a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55}}{c_{44}}} x_2}{\cosh \frac{k\pi}{2a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55}}{c_{44}} b}} \right) \cdot \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1 \quad (105)$$

- Next task is the calculation of the torsion stiffness (see also eq. (83))

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Starting with the energy of the twisted rod we detail eq. (29)

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} S_{ik} T_{ik} = \frac{1}{2} (S_{13} T_{13} + S_{31} T_{31} + S_{23} T_{23} + S_{32} T_{32})$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2 \cdot 2} (S_5 T_5 + S_5 T_5 + S_4 T_4 + S_4 T_4) = \frac{1}{2} (S_5 T_5 + S_4 T_4)$$

- Inserting the strains from eq. (92) and the auxiliary stress function (see eq. (93)) we get:

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{T_5}{c_{55}} T_5 + \frac{T_4}{c_{44}} T_4 \right) = \frac{1}{2c_{55}} g_3^2 \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2c_{44}} g_3^2 \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \quad (106)$$

- Torsion energy per length requires the integration over the rod's cross-section S

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} g_3^2 \iint_S \left[\frac{1}{c_{55}} \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{c_{44}} \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \right] dx_1 dx_2$$

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} g_3^2 \left\{ \int_0^a \left[\left. \frac{1}{c_{55}} \left(x \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2} \right) \right]_{x_2 = -\frac{b}{2}}^{x_2 = \frac{b}{2}} - \int_{-\frac{b}{2}}^{\frac{b}{2}} \frac{1}{c_{55}} \left(x \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_2^2} \right) dx_2 \right] dx_1 + \int_{-\frac{b}{2}}^{\frac{b}{2}} \left[\left. \frac{1}{c_{44}} \left(x \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1} \right) \right]_{x_1 = 0}^{x_1 = a} - \int_0^a \frac{1}{c_{44}} \left(x \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^2} \right) dx_1 \right] dx_2 \right\}$$

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- The function χ is identical to zero on the circumference, and consequently the terms $\left(x \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1}\right)$, $\left(x \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2}\right)$ are also zero.

- Further we get:
$$\eta = - \iint_S \frac{1}{2} g_3^2 \frac{1}{c_{55}} \chi \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_2^2} dx_2 dx_1 - \iint_S \frac{1}{2} g_3^2 \frac{1}{c_{44}} \chi \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^2} dx_1 dx_2$$

$$\eta = -\frac{1}{2} g_3^2 \iint_S \left(\frac{1}{c_{55}} \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{1}{c_{44}} \frac{\partial^2 \chi}{\partial x_1^2} \right) \chi dx_1 dx_2$$

- The expression in brackets represents the differential equation (eq.(95)) and amounts exactly to -2 (depends only on the cross-section).

$$\eta = g_3^2 \iint_S \chi \cdot dx_1 dx_2 = \frac{1}{2} C \cdot g_3^2 \Rightarrow C = 2 \iint_S \chi \cdot dx_1 dx_2 \quad (107)$$

- To calculate the total energy of the entire rod, integration along the rod's axis is required. Use was also made of eq. (107).

$$\eta_{rod} = \int_0^l \eta \cdot dx_3' = \int_0^l \frac{C'}{2} \cdot g_3'^2 \cdot dx_3' = \frac{C'}{2} \cdot g_3'^2 \cdot l = \frac{C'}{2} \cdot \frac{\varphi_3'^2}{l^2} \cdot l = \frac{C'}{2} \cdot \frac{\varphi_3'^2}{l} \quad (108)$$

Note: Now we are going to use the apostrophes again, in order to express that we are still moving within the special SoC

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- The potential energy of a rod twisted by an external torque M ($M=D\varphi$) (109) can be generally expressed as follows:

$$\eta_{pot} = \int_0^{\varphi} \vec{M} \cdot d\vec{\varphi}_3 = \int_0^{\varphi} D' \cdot \vec{\varphi}_3 \cdot d\vec{\varphi}_3 = \frac{1}{2} D' \cdot \varphi_3'^2 \quad (110)$$

- Comparing eqs. (108) & (110) we find: $D' = \frac{C'}{l} = \frac{M}{\varphi}$ with l being the length of the rod. C' is called torsion stiffness (see also eq. (83)). (111)

- Now we need to calculate composition of C' , which is acc. to eq. (107)

$$C' = 2 \iiint_S \chi \cdot dx_1' dx_2' = 2 \int_{-\frac{b}{2}}^{\frac{b}{2}} \int_0^a \frac{8a^2 c_{44}'}{\pi^3} \cdot \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^3} \left(1 - \frac{\cosh \frac{k\pi}{a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55}'}{c_{44}'} x_2'}}{\cosh \frac{k\pi}{2a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55}'}{c_{44}'} b}} \right) \cdot \sin \frac{k\pi}{a} x_1' \cdot dx_1' dx_2'$$

$$C' = C_{x_3'} = \frac{32a^3 c_{44}'}{\pi^4} \cdot \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^3} \left(b - \frac{2a}{k\pi} \sqrt{\frac{c_{44}'}{c_{55}'}} \cdot \tanh \frac{k\pi}{2a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55}'}{c_{44}'} b} \right) \begin{array}{l} \text{rod axis} \\ \text{parallel to } X_3' \end{array} \quad (112)$$

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- Likewise we find:

$$C' = C_{x_1'} = \frac{32a^3 c_{55}'}{\pi^4} \cdot \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^3} \left(b - \frac{2a}{k\pi} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55}'}{c_{66}'}} \cdot \tanh \frac{k\pi}{2a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{66}'}{c_{55}'}} b \right) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{road axis} \\ \text{parallel to } X_1' \end{array} \quad (113)$$

$$C' = C_{x_2'} = \frac{32a^3 c_{66}'}{\pi^4} \cdot \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^3} \left(b - \frac{2a}{k\pi} \sqrt{\frac{c_{66}'}{c_{44}'}} \cdot \tanh \frac{k\pi}{2a} \sqrt{\frac{c_{44}'}{c_{66}'}} b \right) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{road axis} \\ \text{parallel to } X_2' \end{array} \quad (114)$$

- It needs to be mentioned that the case of a square cross-section is covered, if we put simply: $a=b$
- Putting everything together (eqs. (108)-(114)) we can imagine to have the following experimental approach / setup:
 - The rod (dimensions: a, b, l) with defined orientation is excited by a certain external torque M
 - The respective twisting angle φ_i is measured

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- The value of C_{x_i} is calculated according to $C_{x_i} = \frac{I \cdot M}{\varphi_i}$
- Since the C_{x_i} - depending on the PG – frequently consist of two different elastic coefficients, the procedure for the calculation of the single coefficients might be:
 - to use a numerical iteration procedure, or
 - to cut / do an approximation of the series expression for the C_{x_i} such way, that the elastic coefficients can be approximatively calculated
- Special attention has to be paid to cases where the special SoC is different to the crystal-physical SoC (i.e. in cases of special cuts of the rod). Here the elastic coefficients have to be transformed acc. to the recipe (see. eq. (122)):

$$C_{iklm}^i = D_{in} \cdot D_{ko} \cdot D_{lp} \cdot D_{mq} \cdot C_{nopq}$$

and the applicability of the above outlined formalism has to be checked – i.e. the non-existence of : $C_{14}^i, C_{24}^i, C_{34}^i, C_{54}^i, C_{64}^i, C_{15}^i, C_{25}^i, C_{35}^i, C_{65}^i$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

5. Ferroelastics

a: Hysteresis Loop

- A ferroelastic material is characterized by a non-zero spontaneous strain (SS) – analogue to the spontaneous polarization (in ferroelectrics) or to the spontaneous magnetization (in ferromagnetics) – see e.g. the comprehensive overview papers /3/, /4/, /5/.
- A full ferroelastic crystal has at least two Orientation States (OS, domains) which differ in their SS-tensors (/6/).
- Ferroelasticity is the result of a (real or fictive) Phase Transition (PT) from a Paraelastic- (PP) to a Ferroelastic Phase (FP).
- Main (and obvious) differentiator between elastic and ferroelastic behaviour is the dependence of the strain S on stress T .
- Ferroelastics (in contrast to classical elastic materials that follow Hooke's Law) are characterized by a non-linear $S=S(T)$ dependence which is called Ferroelastic Hysteresis Loop.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

T_c : Coercive stress
SS: Spontaneous strain

- Aizu (/6/) derived the specific forms of the SS-Tensors for all possible ferroelastic PTs within the framework of Point Groups.
- As outlined above, in the FP the crystal usually exists in a multi-domain state, whereby the different OSs are separated by domain walls.
- Sapriel (/7/) provided tables with the permissible domain walls for all ferroelastic PTs.
- Ferroelastic domains can be normally observed with the aid of polarizing microscopy because through the ferroelastic PT the crystal system changes (if the hexagonal and trigonal systems are treated as one system)

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

b: Domain Switching (and more)

- Under application of specific external stresses (T^{ext}) the OSs behave differently – they can grow, disappear or even remain as they have been.
- The criterion for a potential change is the value of the interaction energy E^{int} (see eq. (29) and /9/):

$$E^{\text{int}} = -T_i^{\text{ext}} \cdot SS_i \quad (115)$$

- Under the action of the stress the crystal tends to achieve the state with the lowest interaction energy (the minimum).
- Wadhawan (/3/) proposed a simple scheme how to calculate the directions of (compressive) stress to facilitate/generate a certain OS.
- In many cases the stress directions are obvious (see examples below), but sometimes it requires indeed detailed calculations.
- Let's now consider to use the Bending of Rods (see above ch. 4.d:) to record hysteresis loops, and possibly to measure simultaneously elastic coefficients

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- With external bending forces F_0 acting up and down, tensile and compressive stresses interchange in the upper, respectively in the lower part of the rod.
- That means we have got a 'vehicle' that can produce alternating pure tensile and compressive stresses.
- The stresses are not homogeneously distributed across the rod's cross-section, but vary linearly along axis $x_1'(\vec{m})$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

$x_1' = 0$ represents the neutral plane of the rod (stress-free)

$$T' (x_1') = \frac{3F_0c}{4ab^3} x_1'$$

$$x_{T_C}' = x_1' (T' = T_C) = \frac{4ab^3}{3F_0c} T_C$$

$$x_{-T_C}' = x_1' (T' = -T_C) = -\frac{4ab^3}{3F_0c} T_C$$

(116)

- The coercive stress T_C is the applied stress, where an OS switch to another (ref. to the pic above in this chapter, showing the hysteresis loop)
- T_C cannot be realized on the neutral plane, but it should be located in the intervals $0 < x_1' \leq b$ and $0 < T_C \leq T_b$, respectively $0 > x_1' \geq -b$ and $0 > T_C \geq T_{-b}$
- This means, that within a stress-range of $T_C \geq T' \geq -T_C$, which corresponds acc. to eq. (116) to a certain band in the rod with regards to X_1' , no switching of OSs can be initiated. This situation is depicted in the following drawing:

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Remember: In an elastically deformed rod (see chapter: 4.d., eq. (62)) the deviation l of the bar at its end $x'_3 = c$ calculates as:

$$l_e = -\frac{3F_0 s'_{33} c^3}{8ab^3} = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3 E} \quad (117)$$

- But, it must be noted that in the FP we have several OSs, which differ in their orientation with regard to the crystal-physical SoC as set up in the PP.
- Expecting that through the tensile stress in the upper and through the compressive stress in the lower parts of the rod the domain situation is unambiguously defined, but in the grey marked band (see pic above) not!
- In that area a randomized mixture of all possible OSs must be expected

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- This means that for Ferroelastics in the FP the Young Module E, as used in eq. (117), must be treated as an effective \bar{E} , stemming from:
 1. The E-Module of the upper part with defined OS-structure
 2. The E-Module of the lower part with defined OS-structure, but (generally) different from 1.
 3. The E-Module of the grey band with unknown OS-structure

- To this end we need to adjust eq. (117) using \bar{E} :

$$I_e = -\frac{3F_0 s'_{33} c^3}{8ab^3} = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3 \bar{E}} \quad (118)$$

- In Ferroelastics in addition we have to consider the spontaneous strains (SSs), that might occur along the rod's axis, and consequently will contribute to the overall deviation/bending of the rod.
- Those contributions will (generally) differ in the upper and lower parts, and of course depend on the strength and on the direction of the externally applied force.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- It is required to calculate those contributions to I of eqs. (117,118).
- l_u and l_l are the lengths of the rod's upper and lower parts, and x_3' varies between 0 and c

$$\vec{\varphi}' = -\frac{l_l}{r} \vec{n} = -\frac{l_u}{r+2b} \vec{n}$$

$$\rightarrow r = \frac{2b}{\frac{l_u}{l_l} - 1}$$

$$\rightarrow \vec{\varphi}' = -\frac{x_3'}{2b} (S^u - S^l) \vec{n}$$

- Using the same procedure as previously we get the rod deviation caused by strains (subscript S):

$$\varphi_2 \approx \frac{\Delta x_1'}{\Delta x_3'} = \frac{dx_1'}{dx_3'}$$

$$I_S = x_1' (x_3' = c) = \int_0^c \varphi_2' (x_3') dx_3' = -\int_0^c \frac{x_3'}{2b} (S^u - S^l) dx_3' = -\frac{c^2}{4b} (S^u - S^l) \quad (119)$$

Note 1: S^u stands for the strain in the upper part and S^l in the lower part, respectively

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- As already mentioned above, in the FP the particular arrangement of the OSs results in different Young's Moduli in the different parts of the rod. (This creates a significant difference to the considerations made in chapter 4.d., where no spatial distribution of the E-Module is present)

- From eq. (55):
$$s'_{\lambda} = s'_{\lambda 3} \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} x'_1 \rightarrow s'_3 = s'_{33} \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} x'_1$$

- Denoting the elastic coefficients acc. to the rod's parts, we get

$$\text{upper part} \rightarrow s'_{33}{}^u$$

$$\text{lower part} \rightarrow s'_{33}{}^l$$

- The strains on the edges of the parts are written:

$$\text{upper part} \rightarrow s'_3{}^u (x'_1 = b) = s'_{33}{}^u \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} b$$

$$\text{lower part} \rightarrow s'_3{}^l (x'_1 = -b) = -s'_{33}{}^l \frac{3F_0 c}{4ab^3} b$$

- Making use of eq. (119) we have:

$$l_e = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s'_{33}{}^u + s'_{33}{}^l)}{2} \tag{120}$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Finally the total deviation from the rod's axis is obtained when the contribution from the SSs are added (S^u, S^l in eq. (119) just need to be replaced by the SSs: SS^u, SS^l):

$$I_{tot} = I_e + I_{SS} = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)}{2} - \frac{c^2}{4b} (SS^u - SS^l) \quad (121)$$

Example I: ferroelastic species 4mmFmm2

- For the lattice parameters in the FP (PG mm2) it is assumed $a \parallel x$ is greater than a of the tetragonal PP, and $b \parallel y$ is smaller than a of the PP. $c \parallel z$ is not relevant here.
- Therefore schematically the 2 OSs are arranged as follows regarding the crystal-physical SoC. They differ by a rotation of 90° around the z-axis.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

$$SS_{OS1} = \begin{pmatrix} w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -w & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{rotation by } 90^\circ \text{ around } z} SS_{OS2} = \begin{pmatrix} -w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & w & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad w = \frac{1}{2}(S_1 - S_2)$$

- The transformation of the tensors of the spontaneous strains was done with the aid of the rotation matrix (angle α) around the z-axis:

$$D_{kl} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{acc. to the recipe: } (SS)_{kl} = D_{ki} D_{lm} (SS)_{im} \quad (122)$$

- Since $w = \frac{1}{2}(S_1 - S_2) > 0$ in this particular case, tension favours OS 1 and compression OS 2 (because the interaction energy is minimal, respectively)

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- According to eq. (29,115) the interaction energy is defined as:

$$E^{\text{int}} = -T_i^{\text{ext}} \cdot SS_i \quad (123)$$

- Goal is to find the minimum, whereby tension is counted positive, compression negative and shear positive, if the shear angle decreases
- First we have to achieve a defined (preferable mono-domain) state in the upper and lower parts of the rod.
- This can be materialized via an applied force F_0 of suitable strength that initiates the switching of domains into the desired state(s).
- Afterwards the force shall be removed and the domains are expected to remain in the defined status.

- According to eq. $I_{\text{tot}} = I_e + I_{SS} = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)}{2} - \frac{c^2}{4b} (SS^u - SS^l)$ (124)

the bar shall be afterwards excited by F_0 and the rod's deviation I_e as linear function of the force allows to calculate the elastic coefficient $(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)$ along the rod axis.

- Switching of OSs must not happen when F_0 is applied, i.e. the force to measure the elastic coefficients must be small.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- In relation to the crystal-physical SoC we have:

$$s_{33}^u = s_{11}^u = s_{1111} = s_{11} \quad \text{and} \quad s_{33}^l = s_{22}^l = s_{2222} = s_{22} \quad \text{for Case A} \quad (125)$$

whereby for Case B just the superscripts u and l need to be interchanged.

- Finally we have:

$$l_e = -\frac{3F_0c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{11} + s_{22})}{2} \quad \text{for Case A}$$
 and

$$l_e = \frac{3F_0c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{22} + s_{11})}{2} \quad \text{for Case B} \quad (126)$$

- But again with the remark, that not the whole rod unambiguously contributes to the elastic coefficients (because the grey band in the pics above isn't in a well defined state with regard to the OSs).
- Next undertaking is the consideration of the SSs.
- Assuming – as already mentioned above - that an applied force F_0 which e.g. increases gradually and as a consequence, if the stress exceeds the coercive stress in the upper and lower parts of the rod, the OSs should switch and both parts shall enter (ideally) into a mono-domain (or at least well defined) state.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- If then the switching force F_0 is removed the rod are expected to remain bent by the SSs exclusively.

- Using eq. (121) we calculate $I_{SS} = -\frac{c^2}{4b}(2w)$ for Case A and $I_{SS} = \frac{c^2}{4b}(2w)$ for Case B
- Thus the deviation I_{SS} of the rod at zero forces ($F_0=0$) is a direct measure for the spontaneous strain w
- Moreover, this setup should allow to record Hysteresis Loops (also like the forthcoming 2 examples)

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

Example II: $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ - (assumed) ferroelastic Species 6/mmmFmmm (/10/,/11/)

- Lattice parameters at room temperature (in FP with Point Group (PG) mmm)
- $c = 7,728 \text{ \AA}$
 $a = 10.636 \text{ \AA} (\parallel x)$
 $b = 5,993 \text{ \AA} (\parallel y) \Rightarrow \frac{a}{b} = 1,7746$ which is larger than the hexagonal $\sqrt{3} = 1,7320$
- Therefore schematically the 3 OSs are arranged as follows regarding the SoC. They differ by a rotation of 120° around the z-axis.

$$SS_{OS1} = \begin{pmatrix} w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -w & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{rotation by } 120^\circ \text{ around } z} SS_{OS2} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{w}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w & 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w & \frac{w}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\text{again rotation by } 120^\circ \text{ around } z} SS_{OS3} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{w}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w & 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w & \frac{w}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$w = \frac{1}{2}(S_1 - S_2) > 0$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Since $w = \frac{1}{2}(s_1 - s_2) > 0$ in this particular case, tension favours OS 1 and compression OS 2 and OS 3 (because the interaction energy is minimal, respectively) – see also eq. (123) above.

• Again looking at:

$$I_{tot} = I_e + I_{SS} = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)}{2} - \frac{c^2}{4b} (SS^u - SS^l) \quad (127)$$

we first focus on $(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)$, using the transformation of 120° around z \rightarrow

- **OS 1:** $s_{33}^u = s_{11}^u = s_{1111} = s_{11}$ **OS 2, OS 3:** $s_{33}^u = s_{11}^u = \frac{1}{16}(s_{11} + 9s_{22} + 6s_{12} + 3s_{66})$
- These are the results for Case A, whereby for Case B the superscripts l and u need to be interchanged.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Finally we get:

$$l_e = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(17s_{11} + 9s_{22} + 6s_{12} + 3s_{66})}{32} \quad \text{for Case A}$$

and

$$l_e = \frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(17s_{11} + 9s_{22} + 6s_{12} + 3s_{66})}{32} \quad \text{for Case B}$$

- Now step is to investigate the spontaneous strains:

- Using eq. (127) we calculate $l_{SS} = -\frac{c^2}{4b} \left(\frac{3}{2} w \right)$ for Case A and $l_{SS} = \frac{c^2}{4b} \left(\frac{3}{2} w \right)$ for Case B

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

Example III: Rochelle Salt - ferroelastic Species 222F2 (/12/)

- Lattice parameters at 323 K (in PP with Point Group (PG) 222)
 $b = 11,924 \text{ \AA} (\parallel y)$; $a = 14,298 \text{ \AA} (\parallel x)$; $c = 6,230 \text{ \AA} (\parallel z)$
- Lattice parameters at 274 K (in FP with Point Group (PG) 2)
 $b = 11,869 \text{ \AA}$; $a = 14,316 \text{ \AA}$; $c = 6,223$; $\alpha(a,c) = 89,26^\circ$
 (the 2-fold b-axis being also a ferroelectric axis)
- In the FP we shall have 2 OSs as follows regarding the SoC. They differ by a 2-fold rotation around the x- or z-axis

*) Note: Shear components of the strain tensor are counted positive if the shear angle α decreases under action of a shear stress.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Since the SS-Tensors of the two OSs do not possess components in x-direction, no interaction with the tensile nor compressive stress shall be possible in the bar, and therefore also no domain switching.
- The way forward would be to try to rotate the crystal around y, thus the desired SS-strain components would appear.
- To this end let's rotate the crystal with regard to the SoC by 45° counter clock-wise around y
- Applying the related rotation matrix and the recipe (see eq. (122)):

$$D_{kl} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & 0 & \sin \alpha \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & 0 & \cos \alpha \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad (SS)_{kl} = D_{ki} D_{lm} (SS)_{im}$$

we get the rotated strain tensors, which now possess components in x-direction (i.e. along the rod axis)

$$SS_{os1} = \begin{pmatrix} w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -w \end{pmatrix} \quad SS_{os2} = \begin{pmatrix} -w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & w \end{pmatrix} \quad w = \frac{1}{2} S_5$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- It is obvious that under the assumption $w = s_{13} = \frac{1}{2}s_5 > 0$, tension (Case A: upper part) favours **OS 1** and compression (Case A: lower part) **OS 2** (because the interaction energy has to be at minimum – see eq. (115)).

- Again looking at:
$$I_{tot} = I_e + I_{SS} = -\frac{3F_0c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)}{2} - \frac{c^2}{4b} (SS^u - SS^l) \quad (128)$$

we first focus on $(s_{33}^u + s_{33}^l)$, using the transformation of 45° around y and for OS 2 additionally of 180° around z we get:

$$\text{for OS 2: } s_{33}^u = s_{11}^u = \frac{1}{4}(s_{11} + s_{33} + 2s_{13} + 2s_{15} + 2s_{35} + s_{55})$$

$$\text{for OS 1: } s_{33}^l = s_{11}^l = \frac{1}{4}(s_{11} + s_{33} + 2s_{13} - 2s_{15} - 2s_{35} + s_{55})$$

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- Finally we have:

$$I_e = -\frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{11} + s_{33} + 2s_{13} + s_{55})}{4} \quad \text{for Case A}$$

and

$$I_e = \frac{3F_0 c^3}{8ab^3} \cdot \frac{(s_{11} + s_{33} + 2s_{13} + s_{55})}{4} \quad \text{for Case B} \quad (129)$$

- But again with the remark that not the whole rod unambiguously contributes to the elastic coefficients (because the grey band in the pics above isn't in a defined state with regard to the OSs).
- Next undertaking is the consideration of the SSs.
- Assuming – as already mentioned above - that an applied force F_0 which e.g. increases gradually and as a consequence, if the stress exceeds the coercive stress in the upper and lower parts of the rod, the OSs should switch and both parts shall enter (ideally) into a monodomain (or at least well defined) state.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- If then the switching force F_0 is removed the rod is expected to remain bent by the SSs exclusively.

- Taking into account that $w = S_{13} = \frac{1}{2}S_5 > 0$ and using eq. (128) we calculate

$$\begin{aligned} \text{for Case A:} \quad I_{SS} &= -\frac{c^2}{4b}(2w) = -\frac{c^2}{2b}w \\ \text{and} \\ \text{for Case B:} \quad I_{SS} &= \frac{c^2}{4b}(2w) = \frac{c^2}{2b}w \end{aligned}$$

- Thus the deviation I_{SS} of the rod at zero forces ($F_0=0$) is a direct measure for the spontaneous strain $w=S_{13}$

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c: Torsion Pendulum I.

- A pendulum shall be a device where an oscillating torque excites a (round) rod to get it (alternating) twisted by a certain angle.
- Based on the considerations made in chapter 4. (e: Torsion of Rods) an elastic pendulum (e.g. /13/) can be the means to measure shear moduli as well as spontaneous strains SSs (latter of ferroelastics).
- At a first glance it becomes obvious that crystals are promising candidates that exhibit ferroelastic behaviour accompanied by SSs that are pure shear strains.
- According to /6/,/7/ following ferroelastic species are candidates (selection only): 422F222, 4mmFmm2, 4/mmmFmmm, 422F2, 222F2, ...
- Let's look at Rochelle Salt - see chapter 5. (b: Domain Switching (and more), example III).
- Having the torsion angle (see eq. (83)) at the end of the round rod of length l in dependence on the exciting torque and of the elastic compliance moduli:

$$\varphi_3(x_3 = l) = \frac{M \cdot l}{\pi R^4} (s'_{44} + s'_{55}) \quad (130)$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- The orientation of the crystal regarding the rod's special SoC $\vec{m}, \vec{n}, \vec{q}$ shall be as follows:

- We have for **OS 2**: $s'_{44} = 4s'_{2323} = 4s_{2323}$ and $s'_{55} = 4s'_{1313} = 4s_{1313}$
 and for **OS 1**: $s_{44} = 4s_{2323} = 4s_{2323}$ and $s_{55} = 4s_{1313} = 4s_{1313}$

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- Since the crystal behaves uniformly regarding the torsion (i.e. OS 1 and OS 2 do not differ in their the elastic coefficients), the sum $[s_{44} + s_{55}]$ can be precisely measured (see eq. (83)), even in a not-mono-domain state (but in latter case add'l. contributions to the elastic coefficients from the domain walls should be expected).
- If the position of the crystal in the rod is another one than depicted, a corresponding transformation of the elastic coefficients (from one to the other SoC) has to be performed
- The situation is getting more complicated if we now look at the spontaneous strains (SSs)
- When the ferroelastic PT in Rochelle Salt occurs (species 222F2) and we have the crystal's orientation as shown in the pic above, then the crystal exists typically in a mixture of the two OSs (with unknown spatial distribution).
- Reminder: the stress tensor in cylindrical coordinates (ref. to eq. (73)) reads:

$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} r (\vec{e}_\varphi \circ \vec{q} + \vec{q} \circ \vec{e}_\varphi) \quad (131)$$

Note: The stress tensor doesn't depend on the rod's axis coordinate x_3'

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- This yields that **1)** its value depends only on the radius coordinate r and **2)** any interaction with the (fixed) crystal depends on the angle coordinate φ
- **1)** means that, if we have a coercive stress T_C (as discussed in chapter 5. a: Hysteresis Loop, eq. (116)), with eq. (132) we can calculate a 'coercive radius', which is independent from crystal's orientation.

$$r_c = \frac{\pi R^4}{2M} T_C \quad (132)$$

In the region $r < r_c$ the persisting stress (by value) is smaller than T_C which results in the fact that no switching of OSs shall be possible there.
BTW: The coercive radius will decrease if the exciting torque (M) increases.

- **2)** means that we have to look at the mutual orientation of the stress tensor ellipsoid (see eq. (78)) and the crystal (mono-domain state with **OS 2** shown):

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Exploration in which orientation of the crystal (1...5 in the pic above) the interaction energy between the respective SS-Tensor and the stress tensor becomes minimal, results in the OS that will be preferred and switched into.
- Next step is the calculation of the interaction energy for OS 1 and OS 2 (see eq. (115)).

We use the stress tensor (from eq. (78))

$$\bar{T}_i = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -x_2' \\ 0 & 0 & x_1' \\ -x_2' & x_1' & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with } C \equiv \frac{2M}{\pi R^4}$$

and the SS-Tensors for OS 1 and OS 2 (see previously) are:

$$SS_{OS1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ w & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad SS_{OS2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -w & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with } w = \frac{1}{2} S_5 > 0$$

- The interaction energies amount:

$$E_{OS1}^{int} = -T_i^{ext} \cdot SS_i^{OS1} = -C(-2x_2'w) \quad \text{for OS 1} \quad (133)$$

$$E_{OS2}^{int} = -T_i^{ext} \cdot SS_i^{OS2} = -C(2x_2'w) \quad \text{for OS 2} \quad (134)$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- Now we're going to investigate the individual position 1...5 for OS 1 and OS 2
- The positions differ in their coordinates x_1', x_2' which enter the stress tensor
- We do have for 1: $x_1' = |x|, x_2' = 0$ for 2: $x_1' = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}|x|, x_2' = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}|x|$ for 3: $x_1' = 0, x_2' = |x|$
for 4: $x_1' = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}|x|, x_2' = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}|x|$ for 5: $x_1' = -|x|, x_2' = 0$ a.s.o. (135)

No. / angle	E^{int} (OS 1)	E^{int} (OS 2)	Comment (mind that $w > 0$)
1 / 0°	0	0	OS 1 / OS 2 - no preference
2 / 45°	$C\sqrt{2}w x $	$-C\sqrt{2}w x $	OS 2 preferred
3 / 90°	$C2w x $	$-C2w x $	OS 2 preferred (with deeper energy than in pos. 2 and 4)
4 / 135°	$C\sqrt{2}w x $	$-C\sqrt{2}w x $	OS 2 preferred
5 / 180°	0	0	OS 1 / OS 2 - no preference

- It can be easily shown the same way that in the other (left) side of the rod (i.e. the region where $x_2' < 0$) OS 1 is energetically preferred.

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- All above made consideration base on the fact the exciting torque ($+\vec{M}$) shall be directed parallel to \vec{q} of the special SoC.
- Should the torque be directed anti-parallel to \vec{q} ($-\vec{M}$) then OS 1 and OS 2 swap their roles (“switching”). Those circumstances are depicted on the following picture.

- Looking at the pics it can be summarised:
 - If the torque is positive (counter-clockwise twist as shown on the right hand pic) than the rod is expected to exist in two mono-domain regions (left, right acc. to the special SoC)

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- If the torque is negative (clockwise twist as shown on the left hand pic) than the rod is expected also to exist in two mono-domain regions – but swapped
- As discussed earlier, in the rod there is a region $r < r_C$ where no OS-switching can be possible, because the value of the stress doesn't reach T_C .
- Regarding the angle-dependence of the stress tensor around the rod's axis it has to be accepted that in pos. 1 & 5 no relevant stress prevails (means stress smaller than T_C).
- The stress increases from pos. 1 over pos. 2 to 3 where it becomes maximal, followed by a decrease towards pos. 5
- To identify the regions of the rod where switching can be possible at all, we need to check where the effective stress locally exceeds T_C (taking into consideration not only the absolute value but the value caused by the mutual orientation (angle) between the stress and the crystal's OSs).
- Having the 'stress vector' eqs. (72,75):
$$\vec{T}' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} r \vec{e}_\varphi = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} (-x_2' \vec{m} + x_1' \vec{n})$$

Elasticity of Anisotropic Bodies

- The relevant component lies parallel to $\vec{m}(X_1')$:

$$T_{X_1}' = -\frac{2M}{\pi R^4} x_2' \quad (136)$$

and depends only on x_2' .

- From that we have: $|T_{X_1}'|(x_2' = r_C) = T_C' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} r_C$, $|T_{X_1}'|(x_2' = R) = T_R' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} R$ (137)

- Combination of eqs. (136) and (137) yields:

$$|T_{X_1}'| = \frac{T_C'}{r_C} x_2' = \frac{2M}{\pi R^4} x_2' \quad (138)$$

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- Within the special SoC the stress component T'_{x_1} equals, respectively exceeds, the coercive stress T'_C in the blue bordered regions.
- Therefore switching among the two OSs (incl. monodomainisation) shall be possible exactly only there.
- Remaining parts are idle.

- Now we want to investigate by which angle φ_3 the rod will remain in a twisted state - caused by the acting/prevaling spontaneous strains (SSs) – that means without externally applied torque. Precondition would be of course that the blue regions above have been transferred into a monodomain state beforehand (by a suitable torque, which has to be removed afterwards).
- In pic above we see 4 prominent points, characterised by the coordinates:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 1: x'_1 = -\sqrt{R^2 - r_C^2}, x'_2 = -r_C & 2: x'_1 = 0, x'_2 = -R & 3: x'_1 = \sqrt{R^2 - r_C^2}, x'_2 = -r_C \\
 4: x'_1 = \sqrt{R^2 - r_C^2}, x'_2 = r_C & 5: x'_1 = 0, x'_2 = R & 6: x'_1 = -\sqrt{R^2 - r_C^2}, x'_2 = r_C
 \end{array} \quad (139)$$

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- The displacement vector of the unit cell can be simply drawn for OS 2.
- With lattice parameters a, b, c, and α we have:

$$\vec{s}' = -\frac{c}{\tan\alpha} \vec{e}_x = -\frac{c}{\tan\alpha} \vec{m} \quad (140)$$

- At the end of the rod (length l) we calculate the total displacement to be:

$$\vec{s}'_{tot} = -\frac{l}{\tan\alpha} \vec{m} \quad (141)$$

Remark

- this displacement value is only locally correct at positions ② & ⑤
- In other positions projections are to be considered and yield for the component of \vec{s}'_{tot} along the circumference:

$$s'_{circum} = \vec{s}'_{tot} \cdot \vec{e}_\varphi = -\frac{l}{R \cdot \tan\alpha} x'_2$$

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- Finally the maximum displacements, with +M that twists the rod, are:

for the right hemisphere:
$$\vec{s}'_{tot} = -\frac{l}{\tan \alpha} \vec{m}$$

and likewise

for the left hemisphere:
$$\vec{s}'_{tot} = \frac{l}{\tan \alpha} \vec{m}$$

(142)

- The existing situation is depicted here:

$$|\vec{s}'_{tot}| = \frac{l}{\tan \alpha}$$

- The torsion angle of the rod can be now expressed:

$$\varphi_3' = \arctan\left(\frac{\vec{s}'_{tot}}{R}\right)$$

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- Finally we get with $\alpha = 90^\circ - SS = 90^\circ - 2 \cdot S_{13}$ and with

$$\tan(90^\circ - 2S_{13}) = \cot(2S_{13})$$

$$\varphi_3' = \arctan\left(\frac{I}{R \cdot \cot 2S_{13}}\right) \approx \arctan\left(\frac{I \cdot 2S_{13}}{R}\right) \quad (143)$$

and $S_{13} \approx \frac{R}{2 \cdot I} \varphi_3'$

- Thus through the measurement of the twisting angle φ_3' after respective switching of the OSs the SS (S_{13}) can be determined and Hysteresis Loops recorded – e.g. for *Rochelle Salt*.
- Analogue to eq. (121), it should be recognised that the torsion angle consists of an elastic part (see eq. (83)) and of a portion stemming from the spontaneous strain (eq. (143):

$$\varphi_{3tot}' = \varphi_{3e}' + \varphi_{3SS}' = \frac{M \cdot I}{\pi R^4} (s_{44} + s_{55}) + \arctan\left(\frac{I}{R \cdot \cot 2S_{13}}\right) \quad (144)$$

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Torsion Pendulum II.

- In this chapter we want to investigate the behaviour of a rod with a rectangular cross-section, which shall be excited by an oscillating torque.
- Because of easier preparation of specimens with quadratic/rectangular- compared to circular-cross-sections, respective shapes and experiments are clearly preferred.
- Based on the considerations made in chapter 4. (e: Torsion of Rods) we want to concentrate on the elastic/ferroelastic properties of **(NH₄)₂SO₄** (Species 6/mmmFmmm). This crystal was discussed already in chapter 5. Ferroelastics, b: Domain Switching (and more), Example II.
- The orientation of the crystal (meaning OS 1...3) from page 68 have been (via transformation of the coordinate system) referred to the rod's special SoC $\vec{m}, \vec{n}, \vec{q}$ (see overleaf)
- This also concerns the SS-tensors, where we have now:

$$SS_{OS1} = \begin{pmatrix} -w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & w \end{pmatrix} \quad SS_{OS2} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{w}{2} & 0 & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w & 0 & -\frac{w}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad SS_{OS3} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{w}{2} & 0 & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}w & 0 & -\frac{w}{2} \end{pmatrix} \quad w = \frac{1}{2}(S_1 - S_2) > 0 \quad (145)$$

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- The same transformation has to be performed for the elastic stiffnesses of the orthorhombic OSs 1...3 to express C_{44}, C_{55} (see eq. (112)) through the relevant coefficients referred to the crystal-physical SoC
- According to the 'recipe' (eq. (122)) we get after some cumbersome calculations:

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	$c'_{44} =$	$c'_{55} =$	
OS 1	c_{55}	c_{66}	(146)
OS 2	$\frac{c_{55} + 3c_{44}}{4}$	$\frac{3c_{11} + 3c_{22} - 6c_{12} + 4c_{66}}{16}$	
OS 3	$\frac{c_{55} + 3c_{44}}{4}$	$\frac{3c_{11} + 3c_{22} - 6c_{12} + 4c_{66}}{16}$	

- Since the actual composition of the rod isn't known regarding the OSs, we would – if measuring the torsion stiffness – obtain a mixture of the coefficients as shown in the table above.
- Therefore we should strive to bring the crystal (via suitable external stresses) into a well defined domain status.
- Investigation of the interaction energy (see eq. (115)) together with definition of the stress components (see eq. (92)) and the SS-Tensors (see eq. (145))

$$T'_5 = g'_3 \cdot c'_{55} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_1} - x'_2 \right) \approx -C_5 x'_2 \quad T'_4 = g'_3 \cdot c'_{44} \left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x'_2} + x'_1 \right) \approx C_4 x'_1 \quad (147)$$

yields:

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$$E_{OS1}^{int} = -T_i^{ext} \cdot SS_i^{OS1} = -(-C_5 \cdot x_2') \cdot 0 = 0$$

$$E_{OS2}^{int} = -T_i^{ext} \cdot SS_i^{OS2} = -(-C_5 \cdot x_2') \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} w \right)$$

$$E_{OS3}^{int} = -T_i^{ext} \cdot SS_i^{OS3} = -(-C_5 \cdot x_2') \left(-\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} w \right)$$

Note:

T_4' doesn't interact with the SS.

Sign of x_2'	E^{int} (OS 1)	E^{int} (OS 2)	E^{int} (OS 3)	Comment (mind that $w > 0$)
>0	0	>0	<0	OS 3 is preferred
=0	0	0	0	no OS preferred
<0	0	<0	>0	OS 2 is preferred

(148)

- The essence is that with stresses $\pm T_5'$ a monodomainization towards OS 2, respectively OS 3 should be feasible in the two hemispheres!

(149)

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- As also in the previous chapter discussed the stress depends on the coordinates (see eq. (132)) and in a certain region $r < r_c$ its value is smaller than the coercive stress T_c

Getting the stress vector (comp. eqs. (72,75) and eq. (92)):

$$\vec{T}' \approx -C_5 x_2' \cdot \vec{m} + C_4 x_1' \cdot \vec{n}$$

Assuming that $C_5 \approx C_4 = C$ we have:

$$|\vec{T}'| \approx \sqrt{C_5^2 x_2'^2 + C_4^2 x_1'^2} \approx C \sqrt{x_2'^2 + x_1'^2} = C \cdot r$$

$$T_c = T'(r = r_c) \approx C \cdot r_c \quad (150)$$

- This means that in the grey circle area no switching among the OSs shall be possible. Consequently the domain situation there is undefined!
- Question: Taking into account the specific orientation of the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ crystal, what are the regions where switching can be possible at all?
- Answer: Only stress $T_5' \approx -C_5 x_2'$ initiates switching.

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- Within the special SoC the stress component T'_5 equals, respectively exceeds, the coercive stress T_C in the blue bordered regions.
 - Therefore switching among the two OSs (incl. monodomainisation) shall be possible exactly only there.
 - Remaining parts are idle, as well as OS 1.
- Looking now at a potential measuring strategy:
 - If the torque is positive (counter-clockwise twist as shown on the right hand pic above, see pic (149)) than the rod is expected to exist in two mono-domain regions (left, right acc. to the special SoC)
 - If the torque is negative (clockwise twist as shown on the left hand pic) than the rod is expected also to exist in two mono-domain regions – but swapped

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- But, in the rod's middle there is a region (surrounded in blue) where no OS-switching can be possible, because the value of the stress doesn't reach T_C . The domain situation there is undefined.
- Initially the rod shall be increasingly twisted by a torque $+M$ (or $-M$) with the aim to achieve mono-domain states left and right.
- Subsequently taking away the torque, it is assumed that the domain states regarding OS 2 and OS 3 are conserved.
- If now the rod is subjected to twisting oscillations (small torque, in order not to amend the domain structures), the elastic coefficients can be measured.
- As outlined in table (146) we have the coefficients expressed within the crystal-physical SoC
- This way we can measure the coefficients (which are identical for OS 2 and OS 3), but have to accept, that the contribution of the grey marked area (eq. (150)) is unknown.

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- In particular the amount of OS 1 in the grey area cannot be quantified, and leads to a certain/small measuring error.
- Ultimately with eqs. (111,112) and eq.(146) we get:

$$C_{x_3'} = \frac{M'}{\varphi_3} l = \frac{8a^3 (c_{55} + 3c_{44})}{\pi^4} \cdot \sum_{k=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^3} \left(b - \frac{4a}{k\pi} \sqrt{\frac{c_{55} + 3c_{44}}{3c_{11} + 3c_{22} - 6c_{12} + 4c_{66}}} \cdot \tanh \frac{k\pi}{4a} \sqrt{\frac{3c_{11} + 3c_{22} - 6c_{12} + 4c_{66}}{c_{55} + 3c_{44}}} b \right)$$

- Next we shall check the spontaneous strain (SS). We focus on OS 2 and OS 3 since OS 1 cannot contribute. According to eqs. (14,145) we have the relevant SS-Tensor components:

$$SS_{OS2} = S'_{13-OS2} = \frac{\beta'_{13-OS2}}{2} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} w \quad SS_{OS3} = S'_{13-OS3} = \frac{\beta'_{13-OS3}}{2} = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} w \quad (151)$$

$$\text{with } w = \frac{1}{2} (S_1 - S_2) > 0$$

- The displacement vector of the unit cell can be schematically drawn for OS 2, OS 3 as follows.

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- At the end of the rod (length l) we calculate the total displacement for OS 2 and for OS 3 to be:

$$\text{OS 2: } \vec{s}'_{tot} = l \cdot \tan \beta'_{13} \cdot \vec{m} \approx l \cdot \beta'_{13} \cdot \vec{m}$$

$$\text{OS 3: } \vec{s}'_{tot} = -l \cdot \tan \beta'_{13} \cdot \vec{m} \approx -l \cdot \beta'_{13} \cdot \vec{m} \quad (152)$$

- Finally the maximum displacements, with applied $+M$ that twists the rod, are:

$$\text{for the right hemisphere: } \vec{s}'_{tot} \approx -l \cdot \beta'_{13} \cdot \vec{m}$$

and likewise

$$\text{for the left hemisphere: } \vec{s}'_{tot} \approx l \cdot \beta'_{13} \cdot \vec{m}$$

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- The existing situation is depicted here:

$$|\vec{s}'_{tot}| \approx l \cdot \beta'_{13}$$

- The torsion angle of the rod can be now expressed:

$$\varphi_3' = \arctan\left(\frac{2 \cdot |\vec{s}'_{tot}|}{b}\right) \quad (153)$$

- With eq. (151) we can write $|\vec{s}'| \approx l \cdot \beta'_{13} = l \cdot 2S'_{13}$ and with eq. (153) we get the dependence of the torsion angle on the SS:

$$\varphi_3' \approx \arctan\left(\frac{4 \cdot l \cdot S'_{13}}{b}\right) \Rightarrow S'_{13} \approx \frac{b}{4 \cdot l} \tan \varphi_3' \Rightarrow S'_{13} \approx \frac{b}{4 \cdot l} \varphi_3' \quad (154)$$

- Thus through the measurement of the twisting angle φ_3' - after respective switching of the OSs - the SS be determined $S'_{13} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} w = \pm \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} (S_1 - S_2)$

and Hysteresis Loops can be recorded – e.g. for $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.

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d: Further Considerations

- The considerations in the previous chapters follow the 'thread':
Force → Stress → Strain >>>> Elastic Coefficients (compliances s_{ijkl})
- Only for the torsion of non-square rods the derivation scheme differs:
- Strain → Stress >>>> Elastic Coefficients (stiffnesses c_{ijkl}), but certain limitations apply.
- In the theoretical modelling of ferroelastic PTs (see e.g. /14/) the spontaneous strains play a central role (partly even as order parameter), as well as the elastic stiffnesses (being the inverse tensor components to the elastic compliances)
- At ferroelastic PTs specific (combinations of) elastic stiffnesses show typical dependences on the temperature (and sometimes also on pressure).
- Moreover, to describe a ferroelastic PT with a suitable free energy function, the state parameters are strains (S_{ij}) and polarizations (P_k). Therefore the elastic stiffnesses of interest are those at constant polarization (see e.g. /14/)

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- Also, if – experimentally - elastic compliances are measured, the need arises to convert them into elastic stiffnesses, with the aim to compare with the theoretical models
- This isn't a simple undertaking at all. Exemplarily, here the conversion is provided for cubic and hexagonal crystals (/2/,/15/)

Cubic:

(3 components)

$$c_{11} = \frac{s_{11} + s_{12}}{(s_{11} - s_{12})(s_{11} + s_{12})} \quad c_{13} = \frac{-s_{12}}{(s_{11} - s_{12})(s_{11} + s_{12})} \quad c_{44} = \frac{1}{s_{44}}$$

Hexagonal:

(5 components)

$$c_{11} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{s_{33}}{s_{33}(s_{11} + s_{12}) - 2(s_{13})^2} + \frac{1}{s_{11} - s_{12}} \right) \quad c_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{s_{33}}{s_{33}(s_{11} + s_{12}) - 2(s_{13})^2} - \frac{1}{s_{11} - s_{12}} \right)$$

$$c_{33} = \frac{s_{11} + s_{12}}{s_{33}(s_{11} + s_{12}) - 2(s_{13})^2} \quad c_{13} = -\frac{s_{13}}{s_{33}(s_{11} + s_{12}) - 2(s_{13})^2}$$

$$c_{44} = \frac{1}{s_{44}} \quad c_{66} = \frac{1}{2}(c_{11} - c_{12})$$

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- Also it must be taken into account that elastic coefficients:
 - depend on the (measuring) frequency, and there are numerous measuring techniques available
 - are complex numbers, which consists of real and imaginary parts (focus was here entirely on the real part)
 - are related to specific boundary/measuring conditions:
 - isothermal measurement (in thermal equilibrium)
 - adiabatic measurement (fast measurement)
 - at constant electric polarization (superscript P) – measured at an open circuit. (In the high-frequency limit the elastic coefficients at constant polarization are investigated (see e.g. /16/))
 - at constant electric field (superscript E) – measured at a short circuit (e.g. via an electric generator)

Comment: in non-piezoelectric crystals applies: $s_{ij}^P = s_{ij}^E$ and $c_{ij}^P = c_{ij}^E$

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- At the end a simple experimental setup is suggested to investigate the findings/predictions as discussed beforehand.
- Taking into account all pros & cons of the methods, bending of bars seems to be the most uncomplicated approach (incl. easy sample preparation)
- During the quasi-static bending, simultaneously the crystal could be observed with the aid of a polarizing microscope, thus potentially watching the movement of the domain walls within the process of domain switching, a.s.o.
- A respective device could look like this:

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